

Validation of the Glauber model for centrality determination in small system collisions

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Abstract of the Dissertation

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The nuclear modification factor (R_{AA}) of π^0 s and jets in d+Au system shows a suppression in the most central events and enhancement in the peripheral events. Although we can attribute the suppression to the formation of droplets of Quark Gluon Plasma (QGP), it is hard to model an enhancement due to any known physics effect.

Direct photons are transparent to the QGP medium and travel unaffected through it. Therefore, the R_{AA} of direct photons (R_{dAu}^γ) at high momentum should be unity regardless of the event sample.

In this thesis work, we show that the centrality binned R_{dAu}^γ show mostly similar trends of suppression and enhancement as centrality binned $R_{dAu}^{\pi^0}$. This indicates that the method of centrality determination in small system collisions is biased. Furthermore, we use the R_{dAu}^γ to empirically determine the number of binary collisions N_{coll} in a given event sample. Using this new definition, we observe that the $R_{dAu}^{\pi^0}$ is unity for all event sample except for the most central collisions.

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பிரியமானவர்களே உங்களின் கவனம் இருக்கிறேன்
"நீ தொடுக்காதே"
பிரியமானவர்களே உங்கள் கவனம் இருக்கிறேன்

from *appa*

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Standard Model of particle physics

The standard model is an effective field theory which describes the fundamental elements of the universe, its interaction via three of the four fundamental forces¹ : Electromagnetic, Weak nuclear and Strong nuclear forces, the interaction of the force field with itself and the Higgs mechanism which gives rise to the mass of all fundamental particles (except neutrinos). The full equation of the standard model can be found in [1]. In this section, I will focus on two main aspects of the standard model

1.1.1 Quantum Electrodynamics (QED)

QED part of the standard model Lagrangian describes the interaction of matter particles via the electromagnetic force. It is given by ,

$$\mathcal{L}_{QED} = -\frac{1}{4}F_{\mu\nu}F^{\mu\nu} + \bar{\psi}(i\gamma^\mu D_\mu - m)\psi \quad (1.1)$$

This can be expanded with,

$$\begin{aligned} F_{\mu\nu} &= \partial_\mu A_\nu - \partial_\nu A_\mu \\ D_\mu &= \partial_\mu + iQ_e A_\mu \end{aligned}$$

where, A_μ is the electromagnetic four-vector potential, ψ is the fermionic fields, m and Q_e is the mass and charge of the fermions respectively.

¹Gravitational forces described successfully by Einstein's theory of General relativity is not described by the with standard model of particle physics.

1.1.2 Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD)

QCD part of the standard model Lagrangian describes the interaction of matter via the strong nuclear force and its own self-interactions. It is given by,

$$\mathcal{L}_{QCD} = -\frac{1}{4}F_{\mu\nu}^a F_a^{\mu\nu} + \bar{\psi}^i (i\gamma^\mu D_\mu - m\delta_{ij})\psi_j \quad (1.2)$$

This can be expanded with,

$$F_{\mu\nu}^a = \partial_\mu A_\nu^a - \partial_\nu A_\mu^a - g_s f^{abc} A_\mu^b A_\nu^c$$
$$D_\mu = \partial_\mu + ig_s A_\mu$$

where, A_μ^a describe the strong nuclear force potential, ψ is the quark fields, m and Q_s is the mass and color charge of the quark fields respectively and f^{abc} denotes the structure constants of SU(3) gauge symmetry.

1.1.3 Comparing QED and QCD

Although the QED and QCD Lagrangian look similar, there are some key differences which make their effective interactions and ease of observations wildly different. One of the major differences between QED and QCD is that the QED is an abelian gauge field (the generators of SU(2) gauge group commute) and QCD is non-abelian (the generators of SU(3) gauge group do not commute). This effectively means, Gluons, the force fields of QCD, themselves carry color charge and thus can self-interact whereas photons, the force field of QED, is electrically neutral and thus they can't self-interact. This existence of self interaction term leads to fundamentally different strength of coupling between in QED vs QCD.

Running coupling constants

When one probes an electron from a certain distance and measures the electric charge "e", what we essentially measure is the effective electric charge created by the source electron and the cloud of e^+e^- pairs. Thus the effective electric charge is screened by this cloud of e^+e^- pairs. The closer to the electron we make the measurement, which translates to the energy of the probing particle, the more the electric charge that we measure. Thus the strength of the coupling constant increases with energy.

$$\alpha_{em}(Q^2) = \frac{\alpha(\mu^2)}{1 - \frac{\alpha(\mu^2)}{3\pi} \log\left(\frac{Q^2}{\mu^2}\right)} \quad (1.3)$$

where μ is an initial condition on coupling constant known at a particular energy. This equation thus tells you how the coupling constant changes from an arbitrary μ^2 to Q^2 . Fig.1.1 shows the EM coupling constant as a function of momentum transfer.

In a QCD measurement, when we attempt to measure the effective color charge at a particular distance (or energy), it is screened by the quark-antiquark pairs but it is also anti-screened by the self-interacting gluon pairs. The anti-screening dominates and therefore the effective color charge is larger at larger distance and reduces as we probe it at closer distances i.e., the running coupling constant decreases with increasing energy.

$$\alpha_s(Q^2) = \frac{\alpha_s(\mu^2)}{1 + \frac{\alpha_s(\mu^2)}{12\pi}(33 - 2n_f)\log(\frac{Q^2}{\mu^2})} \quad (1.4)$$

where n_f is the number of active quark flavours and as before μ is an initial condition on coupling constant known at a particular energy. Fig.1.2 shows the EM coupling constant as a function of momentum transfer. At the mass of Z boson, $\alpha_s = 0.1184 \pm 0.0007$.

Figure 1.1: Running coupling constant of the electromagnetic force as a function of the momentum of the probing particle [2].

1.1.4 Asymptotic freedom and Color confinement

As the coupling constant in QCD decreases with energy, at high energies or alternatively as small distances the strength of QCD interactions become very weak. This implies that as $Q^2 \rightarrow \infty$, $\alpha_s \rightarrow 0$. This phenomenon is called

Figure 1.2: Running coupling constant of the strong force as a function of the momentum of the probing particle [3].

Asymptotic freedom. The 2004 Nobel Prize in physics were awarded to Gross, Politzer and Wilczek for the discovery of this phenomenon. Due to this reason, interactions via the strong force can be perturbatively calculated at high energies. Measurement of jets in p+A collisions served as a successful test of this perturbative QCD (pQCD).

On the other hand, at low energies, or large distances the quarks and gluons are always bound together as composite color-neutral objects. This is because the coupling constant at low energies is so high that when a quark, antiquark pair is separated, the potential energy in their flux tube is so high that there is enough energy to create another quark-antiquark pair from the vacuum. This is illustrated by a cartoon in Fig.1.3. As perturbative calculations cannot be applied in this regime, lattice calculations with experimental observations as inputs is typically employed to understand QCD interactions with small momentum transfer.

Figure 1.3: A cartoon illustrating color confinement.

Category	QED	QCD
Number of force fields	Single photon field	Eight gluon fields
Fundamental exchange with leptons		
Strength of interactions	First order	$\alpha_s = \frac{e^2}{4\pi} \approx 1$
Running constants	$\alpha_{em}(Q^2) = \frac{\alpha(\mu^2)}{1 - \frac{\alpha(\mu^2)}{3\pi} \log(\frac{Q^2}{\mu^2})}$	$\alpha_s(Q^2) = \frac{\alpha_s(\mu^2)}{1 + \frac{\alpha_s(\mu^2)}{12\pi} (33 - 2n_f) \log(\frac{Q^2}{\mu^2})}$
Self-interaction term	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>none</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;">Abelian-Gauge theory</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Non-Abelian Gauge Theory</p>
beta function $\beta(r) = -\frac{de(r)}{d\ln r}$	positive (screening)	negative (anti-screening)

Table 1.1: Key comparisons between QED and QCD

1.2 Studying QCD in a lab : Heavy-Ion collisions

Studying strong nuclear interactions is very important to understand the evolution of the universe into the state it is today. QCD holds answers to certain deep questions like nature of vacuum, origin of mass ², radius and spin of a proton etc. To answer these questions we need to create a QCD medium and design experimental probes which can access both the perturbative (pQCD) and the non-perturbative (non-pQCD) region of it. The non-perturbative nature of QCD, as discussed above, is impossible to solve analytically from first principles. Thus, theoretical models need to be built with constraints from experimental data to answer these questions.

Ultra-relativistic heavy-ion collision creates a perfect QCD medium of strongly coupled Quarks and Gluons called Quark Gluon Plasma (QGP) to study strong nuclear force in a laboratory. Both pQCD and non-pQCD can be studied via the hard scattered quarks and gluons at high energies and the strongly coupled gluons at low energies, respectively. In addition to this, the evolution of heavy-ion collisions into final state particles mimics the formation of hot dense matter in the early universe (after the Big Bang) and its evolution into hadron states, thus having a far-reaching impact in our understanding of cosmology.

In this section, we will look at the various stages of the heavy-ion collision and its evolution.

1.2.1 Space-Time evolution of heavy ion collision

The exact evolution of collision of two ions to the final formation of hadrons observed at the detector can be divided into three parts.

The incoming nuclei

The two incoming heavy ions are accelerated to relativistic momentum and thus they are Lorentz contracted ($\gamma \sim 106$ for $\sqrt{s} = 200 \text{ GeV}$) and arrive at the point of collision like a densely packed two dimensional sheet or “pancake”. These collisions are characterized by their impact parameter ‘b’ and the geometry of the colliding nuclei. In any heavy-ion collisions, not all nucleons participate in the collisions. The impact parameter determines the overlap region between the two nuclei (if they are both spherical). Only those nucleons within this overlap region participate in the collision and others that

²Higgs mechanism does not explain mass contributed by Gluon interactions which makes up 90% of mass of the visible universe

aren't within the overlap region are labelled as spectators. An experimental parameter called “Centrality” is used to classify collisions based on their impact parameter and study them as independent classes of events. As expected, those with small impact parameter, known as *central events*, have a large overlap and thus many nucleons participate in the collisions leading to the formation of the Quark Gluon Plasma whereas those with large impact parameter, known as *peripheral events*, have very few colliding nucleons and thus reduces the possibility of reaching the critical temperature and density for QGP formation.

Figure 1.4: Cartoon depicting two colliding nuclei with small and large impact parameters. The nucleons in red are the participants and those in grey are the spectators.

It is a topic of intense research to better understand this initial state of the incoming nuclei. One of the strongest theories today suggest the formation of a “Color Glass Condensate (CGC)”, which is an effective theory of saturated gluons [4]. This theory, if proven, can help in studying heavy ion collisions not by factorising them into hard and soft process but by studying the QCD interactions in the limits of fixed x (longitudinal momentum fraction carried by a parton) with $Q^2, s \rightarrow \infty$ and fixed Q^2 with $x \rightarrow 0$ and $s \rightarrow \infty$.

The collision

The collision of heavy nuclei creates a pre-equilibrium state of local hot and dense medium with energy density above that required for phase transition ($1\text{GeV}/\text{fm}^3$). At low energy density, the kinetic energy of the collision is primarily used for parton production. If the energy density is high, a local thermal equilibrium is achieved and a deconfined state of Quarks and Gluons is created. The exact nature of this state was studied by Edward Shuryak at Stony Brook University and he was the first to coin the term Quark-Gluon

Plasma (QGP) [5]. Not only did he provide a strong theoretical basis for QGP, but he coupled it with experimental signatures that would lead to its discovery [6]. The evolution of this phase can be described by “hydrodynamization”, this is different from thermalization as the medium is not homogeneous and there exists large gradient of the stress-energy tensor. The modelling of this phase and its evolution is still an active area of research. What we know so far is that, this perfect-liquid QGP expands, cools and the medium becomes dilute enough that local hydrodynamic equilibrium is no longer maintained.

Hadronization

When the temperature falls below the critical temperature (T_c) of 155MeV, the system phase-transitions into a hadron gas. In this state the partons hadronize through the process of chemical freeze-out. These hadrons continue to scatter and interact with one another, until the system has expanded enough that the mean free path becomes large and the hadrons stream freely (except for the decay of unstable particles) to the detectors. This step is called the thermal freeze-out.

This entire process is depicted in Fig. [7]

Figure 1.5: A schematic of space-time evolution of a heavy ion collisions

1.3 Particle production in heavy ion collision

In a heavy-ion collision, the low p_T and the high p_T particle production are dominated by soft processes and hard processes, respectively. Due to the highly non-perturbative nature of the soft process, it is typically studied by statistical modelling of a system of particles with thermal origin [8] whereas the high p_T can be described in the framework of pQCD.

1.3.1 Soft processes

The first successful modelling of soft process was done by Hagedorn [9] in 1965 and this is summarized in a catchy slogan, “*We describe it by thermodynamics fire-balls, which consists of fire-balls, which ...*”. Any thermal system can be approximated with Boltzmann-Gibbs statistics where the particle spectra is given by

$$\frac{1}{2\pi p_T} \frac{d^2 N}{dp_T d\eta} = \frac{gV m_T}{(2\pi)^3} \exp(-m_T/T) \quad (1.5)$$

where, g is the spin degeneracy factor, V is the volume, m_T is the transverse mass and T is the temperature of the system. This statistics does not take into account the highly correlated nature of the QGP medium formed in a heavy-ion collision. An improvement on the Boltzmann-Gibbs statistics is the Tsallis statistics [10] which accounts for this long-range correlations and is given by

$$\frac{1}{2\pi p_T} \frac{d^2 N}{dp_T d\eta} = \frac{gV m_T}{(2\pi)^3} \left[1 + (q - 1) \frac{m_T}{T}\right]^{-\frac{q}{q-1}} \quad (1.6)$$

where

$$q - 1 = \frac{Var(T)}{\langle T \rangle^2} \quad (1.7)$$

which is the degree of deviation from thermal equilibrium for the system. In the limit of $q \rightarrow 1$, the Tsallis statistics reduces to Boltzmann-Gibbs statistics. As central collisions have higher energy density and temperature, they are more *in equilibrium* and have tighter correlations than peripheral collisions. This is reflected in the ordering of particle spectra from central to peripheral.

1.3.2 Hard processes

As already mentioned, the production of particles through hard process can be described by pQCD framework. Consider two hadrons A and B with momentum P_1 and P_2 colliding to produce particle X. The cross-section of this collision can be written as

$$\sigma^{AB \rightarrow X}(P_1, P_2) = \sum_{a,b,c} \int dx_1 dx_2 dz f_a(x_a, Q^2) f_b(x_b, Q^2) \sigma_{ab}(p_1, p_2, \alpha_S, Q^2) \times D_c^X(z, Q^2) \quad (1.8)$$

under the factorization assumption [11]. This means that the overall nuclei cross-section can be factorised into

- The colliding hadrons can be characterized by its partons and their parton distribution function (PDFs) : $f_a(x_a, Q^2) f_b(x_b, Q^2)$. These PDFs are functions of the longitudinal momentum carried by the interacting hadrons, $p_1 = x_1 P_1$ and $p_2 = x_2 P_2$.
- The cross-section of the parton interaction $\sigma_{ab}(p_1, p_2, \alpha_S, Q^2)$, which can be calculated order-by-order by perturbative theory.
- The fragmentation function, $D_c^X(z, Q^2)$ which is the probability of the parton fragmenting into a final state particle X carrying momentum fraction z of the parton.

Figure 1.6: A schematic of cross-section of two hadrons collision into two final state particles.

These high- p_T particle spectra can also be equivalently described by their statistics by a power law given by

$$\frac{1}{2\pi p_T} \frac{d^2 N}{dp_T d\eta} = \frac{gV m_T}{(2\pi)^3} \left[1 + \frac{m_T}{p_0}\right]^{-n} \quad (1.9)$$

Eq. 1.6 and 1.9 are related to each other for $n = 1/(q - 1)$ and $p_0 = nT$ [12]. Also note, that spectra of heavier particles fall more steeply than lighter particles.

1.3.3 Special note on direct γ production

Direct photons is an umbrella term to denote all other photons in a heavy-ion collision apart from photons from decay of hadrons ($\pi^0 \rightarrow \gamma\gamma$, $\eta \rightarrow \gamma\gamma$ etc.). Different sub-categories of direct photons are shown in Fig. 1.7. Each of these are briefly explained below. More details can be found in [13] and its references.

- **Prompt** : Photons produced from initial hard scattering which includes gluon Compton scattering ($gg \rightarrow g\gamma$) and quark-antiquark annihilation ($q\bar{q} \rightarrow q\gamma$). Photons from pre-equilibrium state also contribute to prompt photons.
- **Thermal** : Simplistically it can be thought of as photons from the evolution of QGP or hadron gas. In reality understanding thermal photons is far more complex and more details can be found in [14].
- **Other** : Many other sources create photons in before, during and after the collision. These include Bremsstrahlung from hadrons, decay leptons, jets etc., jet-photon conversions, jet fragmentation and decay of short-lived resonance particles (w, ϕ).

Figure 1.7: Different sources of photons observed in an experiment [13]

Note: Although it can be divided into different sub-categories, experimental observation of this is highly coupled and thus cannot always be neatly separated. Studying direct photons in different kinematical regime helps provide some degree of decoupling. This is illustrated in Fig.1.8. As this is a high p_T photon analysis, it is dominated by prompt photons.

Figure 1.8: Schematic of kinematical regime of production for different sources of direct photons.

Note: Production of prompt photons via annihilation or Compton scattering is a hard process, therefore this can be calculated by the Eq. 1.8. This does not require a fragmentation function, as the photon in these cases are

already in its final state. For photons produced via jet fragmentation, the full equation is used.

1.4 Heavy ion collision vs pp collision

As it is obvious from above, a heavy-ion collision is not merely a superposition of multiple incoherent p+p collisions. There are several differences between them, both in the initial state of the nucleus as compared to a hadron before the collision, during the collision and the final state after the collision. The differences of these two high energy processes broadly fall under two categories.

1.4.1 Cold nuclear matter effect

The momentum distribution of partons inside a hadron is called parton distribution function (PDFs). These have been well studied in a wide range of nucleon momentum fraction carried by the parton x and the energy of the hard scattering probe Q^2 . It is also well established that the nuclear parton distribution functions (nPDFs) are different from PDFs, i.e the distribution of partons in a bound nucleus is different from one in a free nucleon. This modified PDF has an impact of the final state particles produced in a heavy ion collision. Fig.1.9 shows cross-section ratio between a nucleus A and proton scaled appropriately by number of hadrons in A as a function of x .

Figure 1.9: Ratio of cross-section between nucleus A and proton scaled by number of nucleons as function of x .

This shows three different regions of importance. The suppression of particle production, probably due to multi-particle interaction, called the region of *shadowing* ($x < 0.1$), conservation of momentum compensates for the observed suppression called the region of *anti-shadowing* ($0.1 < x < 0.3$) and the

experimentally observed suppression at large- x probably due to short-range correlations, called EMC effect ($0.3 < x < 0.7$) and finally an excess due to Fermi motion ($0.7 < x < 1$).

All of these modifications affect the production of particles in AB collisions.

1.4.2 Hot nuclear matter effect

Particles are created from the scattering of the colliding nucleus via hard processes. These particles have to traverse through the densely coupled QGP medium. As they travel, they lose energy to the medium due to multiple scattering with the quarks and gluons via elastic processes and due to radiative loss from both gluon and photon radiation. The amount of energy loss can be as high as $dE/dx = 1\text{GeV}/fm$ and it depends on the size, lifetime and entropy density of the QGP medium.

Figure 1.10: A depiction of energy loss in QGP medium which leads to quenching of jets in one direction.

Full theoretical modelling of this energy loss is impossible and thus they require inputs from experimental data to constraint them.

1.5 QGP : Experimental Observables and Results

The first study of relativistic heavy ion collision started in 1984 at the Bevelac experiment in LBNL, Berkeley. This reached energy of 1GeV per nucleon, which was not sufficient energy for the creation of QGP. Between 1986-1994, SPS at CERN collided heavy ions at center of mass energy of 8 GeV to 17.3 GeV per nucleon. This was the first experiment which was dedicated to look for QGP-like signature. Although some evidences were already seen at SPS and later at AGS, the first indisputable evidence came in the year 2000 when high p_T particle suppression was observed at the Relativistic Heavy Ion Collider (RHIC) at Brookhaven National Lab [15].

It is now important to look what exactly we mean by “The discovery of QGP”. As the QGP is formed in a very small spatial region of few femtometers and its lifetime is only 10^{-23} s, it isn't directly accessible to the experiments. Instead the formation of such a medium affects the final states of particles detected and these effects can be observed and used to claim whether the QGP was formed and if so, what are its properties.

1.5.1 Nuclear Modification factor of jets, π^0 s, γ s etc.

One class of the final state particles are those created in the early stage of collisions before the QGP formation. These are typically hard momentum partons and are affected by the QGP as it traverses through the medium. These include jets, high p_T direct photons, π^0 s, heavy flavor quarks etc.

The Nuclear Modification Factor (R_{AB}), defined as in Eq.1.10, is a useful quantity to study the modification of particle production in heavy-ion collisions as compared to a baseline p-p collision. It is the ratio of invariant yield of particle produced in AB collision to the invariant yield of particle produced in pp collision scaled by the average number of binary collision ($\langle N_{coll} \rangle$) in that class of events of AB collisions.

If there is no cold nuclear matter (CNM) effect like the modification of nucleon PDF in a nucleus or hot nuclear matter effect like the interaction of produced particles with a QGP medium, the $R_{AB}(p_T) \approx 1$.

$$R_{AB}(p_T) = \frac{(\frac{d^2N}{dp_T d\eta})_{AB}}{\langle N_{coll} \rangle_{AB} * (\frac{d^2N}{dp_T d\eta})_{pp}} = \frac{Y(AB)}{\langle N_{coll} \rangle_{AB} * Y(pp)} \quad (1.10)$$

Deviations from unity is used to study both initial and final state differences between AB and pp collisions. $R_{AB} < 1$ ($R_{AB} > 1$) is called *suppression*

(*enhancement*) and it implies fewer (more) particles are produced in AB collision as compared to naively scaled up pp collision.

Figure 1.11: Jet formed via hard scattering is quenched by the formation of QGP medium

Experimental Results

The first significant result which confirmed the formation of QGP was published in 2002 [15]. The results present a clear suppression of charged hadrons and π^0 R_{AA} in central Au+Au collision at $\sqrt{s} = 130 \text{ GeV}$ by a factor of about 5. This coupled with results showing lack of suppression in R_{dAu} of π^0 s at high p_T published in 2003 [16] showed that the suppression observed in R_{AA} could not be attributed to cold nuclear matter effects and is indeed an effect of QGP formation. In Fig. [17], the compilation of results from R_{AA} of different particles are shown. Similar results were also obtained by STAR, PHOBOS and BRAHMS collaborations, other detector groups at RHIC.

The CMS experiment also observed the R_{AA} of different particles in Pb+Pb collision over a wide range of transverse momentum and observed a similar suppression of baryons and mesons and lack of suppression of photons.

Figure 1.12: R_{AA} of different particles in central Au+Au collision at 200 GeV [17].

Figure 1.13: R_{AA} of various particles in Pb+Pb collision at $\sqrt{s} = 5.02 \text{ TeV}$ from the CMS experiment [18].

1.5.2 Anisotropic flow v_n

Another observable of final state particles is their azimuthal distribution. Studying the particle yields as a function of azimuth, their anisotropies and correlations teach us about the interaction within the medium and the evolution of the medium through various stages. The study of anisotropic flow falls under this category.

The expansion of QGP is described by relativistic viscous hydrodynamics. The colliding region of high temperature and high density leads to the presence of a region of high thermal pressure. As this medium sits in a region of vacuum with no pressure, it expands rapidly with a velocity of $\langle\beta_T\rangle$. This expansion is termed as “radial flow”. This flow depends on the size of QGP droplet, geometry of collision, temperature and the lifetime of the medium. Comparing the particle yield of different species at different energy and using the blast-wave model, the value of $\langle\beta_T\rangle$ is obtained. The shifting of the p_T spectrum to higher

value due to the expansion of the QGP is called “hardening” of the particle p_T . In non-central collision, the overlap region can be almond shaped as shown in Fig. 1.15. This initial spatial anisotropy leads to asymmetric expansion of the QGP. This modulates the radial flow to azimuthally anisotropic flow in momentum space of final particles. This effect is further amplified when the colliding ions are asymmetric as shown in Fig.1.16. Therefore the presence of anisotropic flow in final particles is an indication of creation of QGP in a collision. This flow is studied by Fourier decomposition of event averaged azimuthal yield of particles, either integrated or as a function of transverse momentum p_T .

$$\frac{dN}{d\phi} \propto 1 + 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} v_n \cos n(\phi - \psi_{RP}) \quad (1.11)$$

where ϕ is the azimuthal angle of the particle, ψ_{RP} is the angle of the reaction plane and v_n is different coefficient of the flow. The second (v_2) and third-order (v_3) are typically called the *elliptical flow* and the *triangular flow*.

Experimental Results

Azimuthal anisotropy or flow of mesons and baryons have been observed at RHIC and LHC. And these flow results and the observed mass ordering at low p_T agrees well with the hydrodynamical model of QGP evolution as shown in Fig. 1.14.

Figure 1.14: Elliptical flow result from PHENIX, STAR and ALICE collaboration [18]

1.5.3 Quarkonium suppression

A characteristic property of any plasma is its Debye screening length. In an electromagnetic plasma, it is the length beyond which a constituent of the plasma cannot exert its influence. For QGP, the analogue is the length beyond which a quark or a gluon cannot exert strong nuclear force. Quarkonium suppression as a probe to test the presence of QGP and to obtain its Debye screening length was first proposed by Matsui and Satz in 1986 [19].

The basic idea of this can be explained with a simple example. Consider the three energy states of J/ψ ($c\bar{c}$), the 1S, 2S and 3S. Let us say the interparticle distance between the quark and antiquark for each of these energy states are d_1 , d_2 and d_3 , the Debye screening length of the QGP is D_{QGP} and

the ordering of the various scales is given by $d_1 < d_2 < D_{QGP} < d_3$. As various states of J/ψ traverse through the QGP medium, due to the screening of the medium, the 1S and 2S states will be unaffected but the 3S state will dissociate. This is because, in this assumed example the $D_{QGP} < d_3$, which means the pair of quark and antiquark cannot exert strong nuclear force as far as its inter-particle distance d_3 anymore and thus they *melt* in the QGP. As the Debye length depends on the energy and temperature of the QGP, the study of sequential melting of various states of quarkonium ($J/\psi, \Upsilon, \dots$) can be thought of as a thermometer probe into the QGP. Note: as compared to other observables, the study of quarkonium suppression is complicated as the suppression due to screening is countered by enhancement due to recombination process.

Figure 1.15: Initial geometry of collision leads to a spatial anisotropy which translates to a momentum anisotropy of final state particles.

Figure 1.16: A depiction of how the geometry of collision affects the momentum anisotropy of final state particles [20].

Experimental Results

STAR collaboration has observed the suppression of both charmonium (J/ψ) and bottomonium (Υ) in Au+Au collision at 200 GeV. But the tracking detector does not have enough resolution to separate them into separate mass states. The sequential melting of different mass states has been observed by CMS collaboration in Pb+Pb collision at 2.6 TeV.

Figure 1.17: R_{AA} of $\Upsilon(1S + 2S + 3S)$ as a function of number of participant in Au+Au collision at 200 GeV [21].

Figure 1.18: Sequential melting of quarkonium states as a function of binding energy in Pb+Pb collisions at 2.76TeV [22]

1.6 Results from small system collisions

The initial motivation to study small system collisions like p-p, p+Au and d+Au was to use these as control experiments to untangle initial state cold nuclear matter effects from final state hot nuclear matter effects, since it was assumed that no QGP could be formed in those collisions. In the early years, the results from these experiments also helped in putting constraints on nuclear modified parton distribution (nPDFs), which helped in mapping out the initial gluon density distribution and its effect on particles which reach the detector.

As mentioned before, the R_{dAu} of π^0 s at high p_T published in 2003 [23] showed no significant suppression, thus validating that no QGP is formed in this system.

Figure 1.19: R_{dA} of charged hadrons and neutral pions in central d+Au collision at $\sqrt{s} = 200\text{GeV}$

However, from the year 2010, there has been growing evidence that QGP droplets are formed in small systems also. This was primarily spearheaded by the observation of the "ridge" (long-range correlations in pseudorapidity) and studies of flow.

This presence of v_2 , v_3 and its ordering by collision size is consistent with the hydrodynamic picture of QGP evolution and thus this is an indication of creating of short lived QGP droplet in small systems [24]. In addition to results from collectivity, there are also nuclear modification plots for jets and π^0 s that point to similar conclusions. In 2016, the R_{dAu} of jets at different centralities was published [25] (see Fig. 1.21). This shows a clear suppression in central collision which is indicative of energy loss in the QGP medium by the jets. However, the apparent enhancement in peripheral collisions has not

Figure 1.20: v_2 and v_3 in p/d/He+Au collisions as published in [24] Fig 3.

been understood. PHENIX results from 2021 [26] of R_{AB} of π^0 s at different centralities for p+Au, d+Au and He+Au also show clear suppression at high p_T . This is shown in Fig. 1.22. Although these results maybe intuitive if we accept the formation of QGP droplet in small systems, the enhancement that is observed is peripheral collisions needs further thought.

This forms the motivation of this analysis and will be discussed in detail along with the fundamentals of centrality determination in the next chapter.

Figure 1.21: Centrality binned R_{AA} of jets in d+Au system as published in [25].

Figure 1.22: Centrality binned R_{AA} of π^0 s for p/d/He+Au and p+Al system. Figure taken from [26].

Chapter 2

Centrality issues in small system collisions

The exact geometry of a collision is determined by the impact parameter (b) of the colliding nuclei. This and related quantities like N_{coll} , the number of binary collisions, N_{part} , number of participant nuclei which is defined as a nucleon which has suffered at least one inelastic collision, aren't directly accessible to us and is in fact derived indirectly from the number of charged particle (N_{ch}) in an event at a detector in the forward (and backward) pseudo-rapidity. This mapping of N_{ch} to N_{coll} and N_{part} is done using a modelling of nucleon-nucleon collision called the Glauber model.

2.1 Glauber Model

This section will provide a brief introduction to the Glauber model with special focus on Glauber Monte Carlo modelling as this is relevant to this analysis. More details on the history and optical approximation can be found here [27]. This is a theoretical model developed by Roy Glauber in 1958 [28] to formally codify the collision of composite particles in high energy experiments. This model, like many theoretical models make some assumptions and rely on certain input parameters. These are detailed in the next two subsections.

2.1.1 Assumptions

In the optical limit, Glauber model makes various assumptions: (i) Nucleons at high energy travel undeflected along a linear trajectory as they pass through each other without any change in cross-section (σ_{tot}^{nn}) of interaction, (ii) The size of the nucleus is much bigger than the range of the nucleon-nucleon force,

(iii) The motion of the nucleons is independent of the nucleus and lastly (iv) σ_{tot}^{nn} is assumed to be constant regardless of the distribution of its momentum among its partons.

2.1.2 Input Parameters

- **Nuclear charge densities :** These are obtained from low energy electron scattering experiments for different nuclei.

For Au nucleus, Woods-Saxon density distribution as a function of radial distance r , given by Eg.2.1 is used. R ($=6.38$ fm) is the radius of the nucleus and a ($=0.535$ fm) is the skin depth

$$\rho(r) = \frac{4\pi r^2 \rho_0}{1 + e^{(r-R)/a}} \quad (2.1)$$

For deuterium nucleus, the density function parameterized by Hulthen wavefunction is used, given by Eg. 2.2. Here $\alpha = 0.228$ fm⁻¹, $\beta = 1.19$ fm⁻¹ and ρ_0 is obtained by the unitarity requirement of wavefunction normalization.

$$\rho(r) = 4\pi r^2 \rho_0 \left(\frac{e^{-\alpha r} + e^{-\beta r}}{r} \right)^2 \quad (2.2)$$

Figure 2.1: (left) Density distribution for Au and Cu nucleus and (right) distance between neutron and proton in deuteron

- **Inelastic nucleon-nucleon cross section (σ_{inel}):** This parameter is important to understand nucleon collisions at different energies but can-

not be computed from first principles as this is in the non-perturbative QCD regime. Thus this needs to be obtained from experimental data of p+p and $p + \bar{p}$ collisions. At RHIC energies, σ_{inel} isn't directly measured. It is obtained by the subtracting experimental data of elastic cross-section (σ_{el}) from total cross-section (σ_{total}). At $\sqrt{s} = 200\text{GeV}$, $\sigma_{inel}^{NN} \approx 42\text{mb}$.

Figure 2.2: σ_{el} , σ_{inel} , σ_{total} from p+p and $p + \bar{p}$ collisions with fits [29].

2.1.3 Monte Carlo framework

Given the input parameters, quantities like N_{coll} and N_{part} can be calculated analytically under the optical approximation of Glauber Model. It is much easier to do so using Glauber Monte Carlo (GMC) and all major experiments use this method today.

In the GMC first the two nuclei are built from the corresponding nucleons by positioning them in a volume randomly, according to the nuclear density distribution (e.g. Woods-Saxon for Au). Note that the nucleons are spheres of $\sqrt{\sigma_{inel}^{NN}/\pi}$ radius, and most of the nuclear volume is empty. Next the center of the two nuclei is placed at a distance b in the plane orthogonal to the beam direction (impact parameter). Now all nucleons of nucleus A are propagated in a straight line through nucleus B along the beam (z) direction. Whenever the centers of the two nucleons from A and B get closer than $\sqrt{\sigma_{inel}^{NN}/\pi}$ we count it as a *collision*. Even if it collided, the nucleon will continue moving along the same straight path, and its chance to participate in a subsequent

collision is not reduced. These are crucial tenets of the original Glauber model. In the end we count the total number of "binary collisions" between nucleons of A and B (N_{coll}), and the number of nucleons that participated in at least one collision (N_{part}). Note that due to the probabilistic spatial distribution of nucleons and the considerable "emptiness" of the nuclear volume, over many events N_{part} and N_{coll} can be quite wide distributions even at fixed impact parameter b .

Fig.2.3 shows a three different GMC events for d+Au collision at different impact parameter. Note that although the deuterium nucleus has only two nucleons, it's wavefunction is almost as big as a Au nucleus.

Figure 2.3: Schematic diagram of a d+Au collision with different impact parameter. This is obtained by modifying Fig 3 in [30]

Using this phenomenological model, we obtain the number of charged particles (N_{ch}) produced at forward rapidity for a particular event. We do this by assuming that on average each nucleon-nucleon collision produces charged particles with the same distribution – a negative binomial, which is notably *not* the same as the one observed in $p+p$ collisions. This "elementary" distribution is then convolved N_{coll} times to obtain the N_{ch} distribution expected for a certain N_{coll} (and, implicitly, b). The procedure is then repeated for all possible b values, with their proper weight, to obtain the final, full N_{ch} distribution observed.

Since we are talking about centrality determination, which is done with the BBC detector in PHENIX, in the text above N_{ch} always refers to the charge observed in the BBC. "Tuning the Glauber Monte Carlo" then means finding the (μ, k) parameters of the "elementary" (nucleon-nucleon) negative binomial charge distribution, which, when convolved with the b (N_{coll}) distributions of the collision describes the charge distribution observed in the BBC in minimum bias events. Note, that in case of heavy ion collisions the charge distribution

in the tuned GMC agrees with the observed BBC N_{ch} distribution very well (within a percent), except the most peripheral events (extremely low N_{ch}).

This N_{ch} is expected to have a monotonic behaviour with the impact parameter (b). Events with small b , known as “central” events produce more N_{ch} in the BBC and events with large b , known as “peripheral” events produce less N_{ch} in the BBC. Run over many different events, an integral of N_{ch} is obtained and this is divided into equal integral bins known as “Centrality bins”. Fig. 2.4 shows an illustration of integral of charged particle as a function of N_{ch} .

Figure 2.4: An illustrated example from [27] which shows the integral of charged particle as a function of N_{ch} and its correlation to $\langle N_{part} \rangle$.

Using GMC, we can generate many events varying the impact parameter. In the Monte Carlo, N_{coll} (and equivalently N_{part}) is calculated by counting the number of overlapping nucleons between the nuclei in d and Au nucleus. This along with the N_{ch} information can help in mapping N_{ch} to N_{coll} . This correlation is illustrated in the top axis of the plot in Fig. 2.4. N_{ch} recorded for an event depends on the collision species and on the specific detector configuration and its placement in a particular experiment. For d+Au collisions at PHENIX, the N_{ch} on the south side of BBC which deposits charge from the

Au nucleus is used.

Once we have this mapping, an event in an experiment is classified into a specific centrality bin based on the number of charged particle in the forward region. Table 2.1 shows the $\langle N_{coll} \rangle$ and $\langle N_{part} \rangle$ for different centrality bins in d+Au collisions.

%Centrality	$\langle N_{coll} \rangle$	$\langle N_{part} \rangle$
0% - 20%	15.10 ± 1.1	15.6 ± 0.9
20% - 40%	10.31 ± 0.7	11.1 ± 0.6
40% - 60%	6.65 ± 0.5	7.7 ± 0.4
60% - 88%	3.21 ± 0.4	4.2 ± 0.3
0% - 88%	7.59 ± 0.5	9.1 ± 0.4

Table 2.1: $\langle N_{coll} \rangle$ and $\langle N_{part} \rangle$ in d+Au collisions for various centrality bins

Note that the correlation between N_{ch} and b is much broader (weaker) in case of d+Au than Au+Au collisions, so the overlap between the derived centrality classes is much larger. This is apparent and becomes important to consider in small system collisions as shown in Fig. 2.5 from GMC simulation of p+Pb and Pb+Pb collisions.

2.2 Is Glauber model valid in small system collisions?

Due to the initial state fluctuations, the dependency of N_{part} to impact parameter ‘b’, needn’t be strictly monotonic. This becomes more apparent in small system collisions. ALICE collaboration studied (i) the N_{part} as a function of b and (ii) multiplicity as a function of N_{part} in p+Pb and Pb+Pb systems [31]. These results are shown in Fig. 2.5 and Fig. 2.6. As it can be seen from these results, for a given window of multiplicity in p+Pb, there is a large variance in the value of N_{part} and therefore the impact parameter, whereas for Pb+Pb the correlation is much tighter.

As multiplicity is used to measure centrality, analysing the 0-20% centrality bin in Pb+Pb is equivalent to studying the class of events with average impact parameter of $b = 3 fm$ with a very small variance. Whereas analysing

the 0-20% centrality bin in p+Pb is also equivalent to studying the class of events with average impact parameter of $b = 3 \text{ fm}$ but with a large variance. This difference implies that we cannot draw equivalent physics conclusions about central p+Pb and Pb+Pb events.

Although I used the example of p+Pb and Pb+Pb to convey the inherent difference between GMC in heavy ion and small system collisions, the conclusions are similar for p/d+Au vs Au+Au system.

Figure 2.5: Scatter plot of N_{part} vs impact parameter (b) in p+Pb and Pb+Pb collisions from [31].

Figure 2.6: Scatter plot of multiplicity vs N_{part} in p+Pb and Pb+Pb collisions from [31].

As mentioned in section 1.6, in recent years there has been growing evidence that point towards a possible formation of QGP even in small systems like p/d+Au collisions [32, 33]. Similar to Au+Au, the R_{AA} of π^0 yield was suppressed in central, but, unlike in Au+Au, it was enhanced in peripheral collisions. There is no known physics mechanism to explain such enhancement. Instead of hypothesizing about new physics, my analysis asks a different question first: is the centrality classification and the Glauber model, as used in

Au+Au, still valid in these very asymmetric heavy ion collisions? In other words, how accurate are we in our estimation of N_{coll} in the above equation. First we present the thought on this question by [30], [34] and [35] and their results from simulation. These are presented in section 2.2.1. Next, we motivate the experimental observable that is used in this analysis (thesis) in section 2.3.

2.2.1 Modelling events with high momentum particles

The initial state of a nucleus varies from event to event due to fluctuations. These fluctuations modify the internal configuration and thus the energy density distribution of the incoming nuclei. Some events have uniform energy density distribution between various nucleons, whereas some events have large concentration of energy in a few nucleons [36]. These fluctuations are not considered in GMC.

Figure 2.7: Two different events showing the energy density profile of Au nucleus. The z-axis is energy density in GeV/fm^3 .

A high p_T particle produced from hard scattering is most likely due to the interaction of a high- x parton in a nucleon with another nucleon. Due to unitarity, if one parton (say a valence quark) carries very high x , higher than average, the other partons necessarily have to be “softer” than usual. This could be thought about through the mechanism of energy conservation or that such a nucleon (with a high- X parton) will have fewer number of partons than average. These two approaches have been studied and modelled in detail by [30] and [34], respectively.

In a large nucleus like Au or Pb, the presence of a high- X parton does not affect the soft particle production much, as there are several other nucleons to compensate for the reduction in soft particle cross-section. Thus an average event with or without a high momentum particle has similar soft particle

production. As the cross-section is similar, the number of soft-particles (N_{ch}) produced in the forward region is similar.

However, in a small system (or small-on-large) collisions, as there are only a few nucleons (at least on one side), the overall soft particle cross-section is reduced. As experiments classify events into different centrality based on the N_{ch} , such an event will be classified as a more peripheral event even if in reality the impact parameter was close to zero. In Fig.2.8 and 2.9 there is a cartoon depiction of the concept explained here. This migration of events only happens in one direction i.e central events migrate to more peripheral events and not the other way.

Modelling energy conservation

An important result from simulations which studied the effect of centrality mis-binning is done in [30]. In this work, they simulate d+Au collision events with a high p_T particle or jets. They bin these simulated events by number of binary collisions and the number of charged particle detected at forward rapidity. Next they obtain the R_{dA} of π^0 s from these simulated events. The N_{coll} parameter in this R_{dA} are obtained by (a) the true number of binary collision and (b) N_{coll} derived from N_{ch} using Glauber model. These results for different centralities are presented in Fig.2.10 and 2.11. The results show that the simulation reproduces the published data very well when N_{coll} is derived using GMC. This is different from the true N_{coll} for reasons discussed already.

Figure 2.8: A simplistic cartoon depiction of Au+Au collision. (Left) A central collision with uniform energy density. (Right) A central collision with one high energy nucleon.

Figure 2.9: A simplistic cartoon depiction of d+Au collision. A) Central d+Au collision with uniform energy density. B) Central d+Au collision with one high energy nucleon on d nucleus. C) a peripheral d+Au collision with uniform energy density.

Figure 2.10: R_{dA} of π^0 from PHENIX publication and simulation with N_{coll} derived using Glauber Model [30].

Figure 2.11: R_{dA} of π^0 from PHENIX publication and simulation with true N_{coll} scaling [30].

Modelling fewer partons in a nucleon with high- X parton

In this model, the cross-section of the hard process, i.e. the production of jet isn't modified but the cross-section of the soft-process is reduced. This can be pictorially thought of as a reduction in size of the nuclei as shown in Fig.2.12. They modelled the change in relative size of the nuclei as,

$$r(x_p) = \exp(-\beta x_p) r_0 \quad (2.3)$$

This results in a nucleon-nucleon cross-section which depends on x_p given by,

$$\sigma(x_p) = \frac{1}{4} (1 + \exp(-\beta x_p))^2 \sigma_{NN} \quad (2.4)$$

At RHIC energies, $\sigma_{NN} = 42mb$. Using this simple one parameter model, the authors of [34] modified the MC-Glauber and compared the obtained results with jets R_{dA} from published PHENIX data to obtain $\beta = 1.38$. Using this they also obtained prediction for R_{pA} and R_{HeA} and report an expectation of 50% suppression in central R_{pA} and 200% enhancement in peripheral collision for $x \approx 0.4 - 0.5$.

This reduced cross-section means effectively smaller N_{coll} . This makes the $R_{dA} < 1$ for central collision and $R_{dA} > 1$ for peripheral collision.

Figure 2.12: Schematic picture of a nucleon-nucleon cross-section when the size of the nucleon is (a) unmodified and (b) reduced.

2.3 Validation of Glauber model in small system collisions using experimental data

In this analysis, we wanted to study if the Glauber Model is a good tool for centrality determination in small system using an experimental observable.

High p_T direct photons [37]. Direct photons for all practical purposes ($\alpha_s \gg \alpha_{em}$) travel unaffected in the QGP medium. Theoretical prediction put the value of R_{AA} to be at unity at high momentum, regardless of the centrality class. The number of high p_T direct photons at any p_T is always proportional to the true N_{coll} of the event, irrespective of whether the event centrality has been classified properly or not. This allows even for the possibility that the event classification has a bias varying with the highest p_T observed at mid-rapidity. Photons being a standard candle means that for high p_T events the proper centrality classification will be the one that makes the direct photon R_{dAu} unity, at all p_T , irrespective of how the event would be classified based on BBC charge (or any other global variable).

Using direct photons to validate results from π^0 is not a new technique. This has been used even in Au+Au collisions. The R_{AA} of π^0 in Au+Au collision when analysed in different centrality bins showed large suppression in central bins and as we move to peripheral collision, the degree of suppression reduces, almost vanishing at peripheral Au+Au collisions. This is shown in Fig.2.13. This makes intuitive sense as the central collision has the largest number of participating nucleons and energy density and thus QGP is formed whereas a peripheral collision is very similar to p+p collision. In 2012, PHENIX collaboration published the monumental result of, R_{AA} of direct photons in different centrality class at $\sqrt{s} = 200 GeV$ [23] which further validated the π^0 results¹ and the hypothesis that high p_T direct photons scale with N_{coll} .

¹In the sense that calculating N_{coll} with the Glauber model in large-on-large ion collisions is justified, since the same calculation makes the photon R_{AA} unity, as expected.

Figure 2.13: R_{AA} of neutral pions in Au+Au collision at $\sqrt{s} = 200\text{GeV}$ in different bins of centrality [38].

Figure 2.14: R_{AA} of direct photons in Au+Au collision at $\sqrt{s} = 200\text{GeV}$ at different centralities [23]

For this project, I am analysing d+Au collisions from data taken in 2016 at the Relativistic Heavy Ion Collider (RHIC). The primary detector used is the Electromagnetic Calorimeter (EMCal) covering pseudorapidity of ± 0.35 in the PHENIX detector system. The primary signals for my analysis are the invariant yield of π^0 s and direct γ s in different centrality bins and their

respective nuclear modification factors.

In addition to this, I will plot the ratio of invariant direct γ yield over invariant π^0 yield for different centrality . This is given by,

$$\frac{Nbin * (\frac{d^2N}{dP_t d\eta})_\gamma}{Nbin * (\frac{d^2N}{dP_t d\eta})_{\pi^0}} \implies \frac{\text{no dependence on centrality}}{\text{centrality dependence due to medium effects}}$$

What will this ratio teach us? If the centrality dependence that we see in π^0 spectrum is because of true physics effects, like energy loss in colored dense medium, then this shouldn't affect direct γ . So the ratio will HAVE centrality dependence. Whereas if the centrality dependence that we see in π^0 spectrum is because of X (possibly some non-physics reason as described before), then this should affect direct γ equally. So the ratio will NOT HAVE centrality dependence. As the production mechanisms are similar for π^0 s and direct γ s in this momentum range. Note, that all initial state effects and cold nuclear matter effects will cancel between numerator and denominator and thus this isn't a good tool to make strong statements on the exact nature of X which leads to the specific results.

The next couple of sections will detail the experimental setup, analysis procedure, results and its implications.

Chapter 3

Experimental Overview

3.1 Relativistic Heavy Ion Collider

The relativistic heavy ion collider (RHIC) is located at Brookhaven National Lab (BNL), USA. It is a versatile machine both in terms of collision species and energy of collisions. Over its 21 years of operation, it has collided various combinations of heavy ions and protons (polarized and polarized) : $p + p$, $p + Al$, $p + Au$, $d + Au$, $h + Au$, $Cu + Cu$, $Cu + Au$, $Zr + Zr$, $Ru + Ru$, $Au + Au$ and $U + U$. The energy of these collisions have also been varied from 7.7 GeV up to 100 GeV per nucleon for ions and 250 GeV for protons. RHIC has two independent super-conducting rings (labelled blue and yellow) of 3.8 km in circumference, in which ions are accelerated clockwise and counter-clockwise respectively. The two rings of the accelerator cross each other at six different interaction points (IP). Here the beams meet in a single vacuum pipe, crossing each other at near-zero angle (“diamond”). As of 2016, the year of data collection for this analysis, only two of these IPs were equipped with detector systems : the Solenoid Tracker at RHIC (STAR) at the 6’0 clock position and the Pioneering High Energy Nuclear Interaction eXperiment (PHENIX) at 8’0 clock position. Older decommissioned detector system include BRAHMS at 2 O’clock position and PHOBOS at 10 O’clock position. The primary goal of this collider and its detector system was to study nuclear matter at high temperatures, high densities and to discover the Quark Gluon Plasma (QGP). Huge improvements over the years in luminosity, the large database, state of the art detector and its analysis has been vital in the outstanding success in achieving its primary goals and pushing our boundaries of understanding the strong nuclear force.

3.2 PHENIX detector

As mentioned earlier, the PHENIX detector is housed in the 8 O'clock position on the ring of the RHIC. It has been in operation from the year 2000 to 2016. This detector is specialised in the identification of electrons, positrons, photons and high p_T hadrons with excellent momentum and position resolution as well as muons at high rapidities. There are two complementary subsystems within this detector system, one at mid-rapidity and one at forward rapidity. For this analysis, we use the global detector Beam Beam Counter (BBC) to obtain parameters of collisions like collision time and vertex, centrality, reaction plane, and we primarily use the Electromagnetic Calorimeter (EMCal) at mid-rapidity to measure photons. Both of these detectors will be discussed in detail.

Figure 3.1: The PHENIX detector layout in the year 2016. The upper panel is the beam view cross-section and the lower panel is the side view cross-section.

3.2.1 Beam Beam Counter

Most high energy experiment have detectors very close to the beam pipe in the very forward and backward region. These provide first level of information regarding the collision : particle multiplicity, vertex (z_{vtx}) and time of collisions t_0 etc. At RHIC, all detectors have identical global detectors, Beam Beam Counter (BBC) and Zero Degree Calorimeter (ZDC), installed in them.

The BBC detector is placed in the north and south arm at rapidity $3.1 < |\eta| < 3.9$, full coverage in ϕ and 1.44m (L) from the mean expected place of collision [39]. This is a Cherenkov detector with each arm having 64 long hexagonal quartz radiators arranged in a honeycomb structure terminating at photomultiplier tubes (PMT). This is shown in Fig. 3.2. BBC thus provides information on both the multiplicity and the precise timing (with $\sigma = 52 \pm 4ps$ for Au+Au collisions) of the arriving particle. Using the average time of flight of particles in north and south arm, (t_S, t_N) we can determine the z_{vtx} and t_0 as shown below:

$$t_0 = \frac{t_N^{BBC} + t_S^{BBC}}{2} - \frac{L}{2} \quad (3.1)$$

$$Z_{vtx} = \frac{c}{2}(t_N^{BBC} - t_S^{BBC}) \quad (3.2)$$

The BBC also provides a level 1 trigger and is useful in centrality determination.

Figure 3.2: BBC detector from one side with 64 radiators and PMTs

3.2.2 Electromagnetic Calorimeter

Electromagnetic calorimeters measure energy deposited by showers created by photon, electrons and positrons. This showering of electromagnetic particles

mainly happens via pair production and bremsstrahlung as they pass through the material of the calorimeter. Energy from a single particle is usually deposited in more than one "tower"; from the energy deposit pattern the impact point of the particle can also be determined.

The EMCal at PHENIX is located about 5 m from the interaction point covering $|\eta| < 0.35$. The entire detector consists of 8 different sectors made up of two different types of detector, lead-scintillator (PbSc) and lead-glass (PbGl). PbSc detectors occupy 6 sectors, 4 on the west and 2 on the east arm, and the PbGl detector occupies 2 sectors on the east side. The smallest unit (individually read out) of the calorimeter is called a tower. Combination of 2x2 towers form a module and a combination of 6x6 modules form the supermodule. These supermodules are further bundled together in units of 6*3 (PbSc) and 8*4 (PbGl) to form sectors (note that each sector is the same size, but the tower size, i.e. the *granularity* of the PbSc and PbGl sectors is different).

PbSc is a sampling-type detector. Each tower in this has 66 sandwiched alternating layers of Pb and plastic scintillator with a cross-section of 5.25 cm x 5.25 cm and total length of 37cm. The Pb layers act as a passive absorber/converter and this induces showering due to its large radiation length, while the scintillator layers are the active detector from which light is collected and observed. The entire detector is woven with 36 optical fibers which are doped to become wavelength shifting for effective collection of light (the mostly UV light from the scintillator is shifted to visible green to match the quantum efficiency curve of the photomultipliers). The amount of light collected is directly proportional to the energy deposited by the electromagnetic particle. PbSc has better linearity and its response to hadrons are better understood. The energy (σ_E) and position resolution ($\sigma_x(E)$) of the PbSc detector as obtained by test beam results from tests at CERN and BNL are,

$$\frac{\sigma_E}{E} = \frac{8.1\%}{\sqrt{E(GeV)}} \oplus 2.1\% \quad (3.3)$$

$$\sigma_x(E) = \frac{5.9(mm)}{\sqrt{E(GeV)}} \oplus 1.4(mm) \quad (3.4)$$

Figure 3.3: A module consisting of 2x2 towers in PbSc

PbGl is a homogenous Cherenkov type detector. Each crystal is made of 55% PbO and 45% SiO₂ with a refraction index of $n=1.648$. Any charged particle that passes through it produces Cherenkov light *if* its velocity exceeds the speed of light in the PbGl ($c/1.648$). For pions, the lightest hadrons, this condition is fulfilled only for momenta above $\approx 4 \text{ GeV}/c$, but near-massless electrons always travel by $\approx c$ and produce light. That means that as long as there is no nuclear interaction (the hadrons pass the detector unchanged), the PbGl is virtually “blind” to them, on the other hand all electrons produce light. As we mentioned above, in the electromagnetic shower many secondary electrons are produced, and their total number – as well as the total Cherenkov-light produced – is proportional to the energy of the original, incoming particle. Contrary to the sampling calorimeter, there are no optically passive absorbers here, so all light produced by electrons in the shower will in principle be visible. This results in better *photostatistics*, improving the energy resolution. Also, the transverse size of the showers is smaller in the PbGl than in PbSc (smaller “Moliere-radius”), thus the towers can be less wide (4*4 cm). This makes the PbGl highly granular and thus provides a better energy resolution. The energy (σ_E) and position resolution ($\sigma_x(E)$) of the PbGl detector as obtained by test beam results from tests at CERN and BNL are,

$$\frac{\sigma_E}{E} = \frac{5.9\%}{\sqrt{E(\text{GeV})}} \oplus 0.8\% \quad (3.5)$$

$$\sigma_x(E) = \frac{5.9(\text{mm})}{\sqrt{E(\text{GeV})}} \oplus 0.2(\text{mm}) \quad (3.6)$$

Figure 3.4: A module consisting of 6x4 towers in PbGl

Subdetector	PbSc	PbGl
Type	Shashlik	Cerenkov
Radiation length (X_0) [mm]	21	28
Moliere radius [mm]	43	36.8
Cross section of a tower [mm^2]	55.3×55.3	40×40
Depth [mm]	375	400
$\Delta\eta \times \Delta\phi$ of a tower	0.011×0.011	0.008×0.008
Number of sectors	6	2
Number of towers	15552	9216

Table 3.1: Summary of the two subdetectors within the EMCal at PHENIX [40].

3.3 PHENIX Trigger systems

3.3.1 Minimum Bias (MB) trigger

Most of the time when bunches cross, there is no activity to record. The ions in the opposite bunches rarely collide. On the other hand bunch crossings occur at a rate of 10 MHz, and it would be not only impractical, but even impossible to read out all detectors at this rate, not to speak about the huge amount of meaningless data stored. Any data acquisition system is looking for “events of possible interest”. So the first step is knowing when the collision occurred. At PHENIX this is done by the BBC, which provides a level 1 trigger. In a heavy ion collision, the BBC looks for coincidence signal in both its north and south detector to establish a flag to denote that this trigger threshold has been met. This is called the minimum bias (MB) trigger. Note: due to low multiplicity in small system collisions like p+p, p+Au and d+Au, the requirement for the trigger is that there are particles in only one of the detectors of the BBC. As

there is a requirement of event multiplicity for this trigger, we do not record and reconstruct the full cross-section of the collision. In the case of d+Au collisions only 88% of the total cross-section is captured by the method of event selection with this trigger.

Even when an actual ion-ion collision happens and it meets the threshold of the MB trigger, most of these collisions are quite similar to one another and thus we don't gain by recording all the data. Thus a "scaledown" factor is introduced here. Only 1 out of n (scaledown factor) events which have crossed the MB trigger threshold are thus recorded, i.e if the scaledown factor is 100, only one in 100 events which cross the MB threshold is recorded. The final spectra are normalised by knowing this scaledown factor. There are three subcategories of this trigger selection based on the z_{vtx} which were active in Run16.

- MB no vertex cut : No cut on vertex of collision
- MB narrow vertex: Vertex cut of $\pm 10cm$

3.3.2 EMCal/RICH Trigger (ERT)

By the above method, we obtain a good sample of data, but we may lose out on interesting events. What constitutes as "interesting" depends on the physics goals of the experiment. For PHENIX, it is important to measure spectra of π^0 s, direct γ , jets as a function of particle momentum. These spectra are steeply falling $\sim p_T^{-7}$ and thus we have to record millions of collisions before we obtain one 20 GeV π^0 particle. To avoid this, PHENIX has a level two trigger called ERT. This uses the information from EMCal and the Ring Imaging Cherenkov detector (RICH) to select on highly energetic particles. The role of the RICH is to give preference to electrons and positrons, since, as we have seen, charged hadrons with less than $p_T = 4 \text{ GeV}/c$ don't fire the RICH. The total energy is calculated by online summing from a 2x2 tower grid. This energy information: large local energy deposit probably from a single particle, can also be coupled with a requirement on the number of photoelectrons from the RICH detector to enhance electrons and positrons in the sample and sets the trigger condition. Note: in later years, the condition on the number of photoelectrons was not used. PHENIX usually records data from different energy threshold and the triggers are conveniently labelled ERT4x4a, ERT4x4b and ERT4x4c. In Run16 only the ERT4x4b was used.

3.3.3 Overview of some trigger terminology

- Raw count : the number events which satisfy a trigger condition

Name	Bit Mask	Scale Down	State	Raw Trigger Count	Raw Trigger Rate	Live Trigger Count	Live Trigger Rate	Scaled Trigger Count	Scaled Trigger Rate	Lifetime
BBCLL1(>0 tubes)	0x00000001	35713	Enabled	447641390	177565.01	423702773	168069.33	11863	4.71	0.95
BBCLL1(>0 tubes) novertex	0x00000002	2993	Enabled	695476227	275873.16	657302252	260730.76	219539	87.08	0.95
ZDCLL1wide	0x00000004	2856	Enabled	199423710	79105.00	191667365	76028.31	67086	26.61	0.96
BBCLL1(>0 tubes) central_narrowvtx	0x00000008	3	Enabled	60754490	24099.36	57555386	22830.38	14388847	5707.60	0.95
BBCLL1(>0 tubes) narrowvtx	0x00000010	14285	Enabled	178862164	70948.89	169325887	67166.16	11852	4.70	0.95
ZDCNS	0x00000020	2856	Enabled	155138474	61538.47	147161429	58374.23	51509	20.43	0.95
ERT 4x4b	0x00000040	0	Enabled	131427	52.13	118527	47.02	118527	47.02	0.90
ERT 4x4a&BBCLL1	0x00000080	9999999	Enabled	206684	81.98	197824	78.47	0	0.00	0.96
ERT 4x4a	0x00000100	9999999	Enabled	241181	95.67	214703	85.17	0	0.00	0.89

Figure 3.5: A example table with details on various triggers and their raw, live and scaled counts from run summary page for run number 454774.

Figure 3.6: A schematic Venn diagram to explain the various trigger terminology.

- Live count: the number of events which satisfy a trigger condition and the DAQ is live, i.e. ready to accept a new event and read out the corresponding detector data (note that this does not mean that the data will actually be read out!)
- Scaled Trigger count : the actual number of events recorded (the ones which met the set scaledown factor).

Chapter 4

Data Analysis

Every presentation or document can be written smoothly if you have a particular audience in mind. For me, the audience is going to be the person doing a direct photon analysis in any collision system/ energy. I have come to realise that no one document can be a one stop answer to everything you should know in order to do your analysis, if such a document can be written, then a program can be written, making the necessity of a physicist unnecessary, which thankfully isn't the case. The issue is not that a *specific* analysis couldn't in principle be documented perfectly, i.e. making it traceable and repeatable – this can be achieved and at best done in the corresponding "analysis note". The issue is that even using the same detector, every new dataset has its own peculiarities; ignoring them and applying blindly the exact steps of an earlier analysis leads at best to sub-optimal, at worst to outright wrong results. A more subtle, but equally important point: we, both as individuals and as a community, learn with time. We learn from past mistakes: some methods used a few decades ago by the most respectable scientists of the time turned out to be misguided, and obviously unacceptable to use today. Some other things were simply impossible back then (for instance there are certain systematic uncertainties that can be reliably studied only if the statistics is sufficiently large). And maybe most important: with time we invent completely new approaches – ideally dictated by the data themselves. I am going to quote what my supervisor Prof. Gabor David told me many times, "Look at the data, they will tell you how the analysis should be conducted. Of course always be careful (even paranoid) about what you do, and always look for consistencies between various approaches." – With that in mind, here are my data and their analysis.

4.1 Flow of Analysis

Here is a brief description of the flow of this analysis, with more details on each step explained in subsequent sections. Before we begin the analysis, the data first needs to be calibrated. This means some basic quality check on various run segments, removing bad signals, correcting for energy and timing signatures, making sure that data and simulation have equal EMCal response etc. Once this is done, the data are ready to be analysed.

As mentioned in the previous chapter, to answer our physics question, we will need an invariant yield of π^0 s and direct γ s. Photon signals from EMCal are used to obtain both of these information. In an event, all photon signals collectively are called *inclusive photons*. These can be subdivided into *decay photons* and *direct photons*. A raw π^0 spectrum is obtained by combinatorial reconstruction of all photons to get the invariant mass. This is then corrected using simulation to obtain a full invariant π^0 spectrum. Fits from global data are used to also obtain invariant η spectrum. Pion and Eta simulations are then used to obtain a raw decay gamma spectrum from each of the hadrons respectively. This is then subtracted from the inclusive photon spectrum to obtain the raw direct photon spectrum. This is then corrected with single photon simulation to get an invariant direct photon spectrum.

Figure 4.1: Overall flowchart of the analysis. Boxes in blue indicate spectra that we obtain from collision data. Boxes in pink are simulation, and boxes in green are derived quantities using both collision data and simulations.

4.2 Triggers

In this analysis, datasets from two triggers are used.

- BBCLL1(>0 tubes) narrowvtx: This is a level 1 trigger. This trigger condition is satisfied when there is a coincidence obtained between the photo multipliers of the north and south BBC detectors. In addition, there is a narrow vertex condition which restricts the trigger condition to only events which collide in the +/- 15cm Z vertex position. In this Analysis note, this trigger is typically referred to as “MB trigger”.
- ERT4x4b : This is a Level 2 trigger. Events which satisfy a minimum energy threshold in a 4x4 overlapping EMCal towers satisfy this trigger condition. For Run16 d+Au collision, the EMCal energy threshold for 4x4b is set to 2.5 GeV.

4.3 Calibration

Before we begin making any sensible physics plots, we need to calibrate and clean up the data. There are three broad categories of calibration/quality assurance done in this analysis.

4.3.1 Dead Hot Tower list

The EMCal detector at PHENIX is divided into eight sectors, six Lead-Scintillators (PbSc) and two Lead-Glass (PbGl). Each of these sectors are divided into a grid of individual towers. The PbSc sectors have 36*72 towers and the PbGl sectors have 48*96 towers.

Some of these towers may malfunction and thus need to be removed from the analysis. We classify the malfunctioning towers into three different types.

- Dead towers : Towers which don't have any hits during a run.
- Hot towers : Towers which fire abnormally often, which could be because of electronics malfunctioning.
- Warm towers: Towers which misbehave in certain energy ranges.

The procedure to remove these towers from the analysis is given below.

Procedure

First, we identify these bad towers and isolate them from the analysis. The steps below will result in a map of Hot, Warm, and Dead towers. Note that our procedure is based on the “tower” THmulf, which is filled only with hits in the central (most energetic) tower of the cluster, rather than all towers included in a cluster “towerhit” THmulf). The two dead/hot maps (DHM) might be somewhat different at low p_T .

- Dead Towers : A 1D histogram of frequency of number of hits for each tower in each sector for MB and ERT-triggered dataset is plotted. Towers which never fired across all energy are marked to be discarded from the analysis.
- Hot and Warm towers: A 1D histogram of frequency of number of hits for each tower in each sector for MB and ERT-triggered dataset is plotted in different energy brackets : [0,1), [1,3), [3,10), [10,30]. This histogram is fitted to a Gaussian curve and all towers which are beyond the $\pm 5\sigma$ value are excluded. Of course at higher energies where the average number of hits becomes small, the -5σ condition is dropped.
- From ERT-triggered dataset, only hit maps in energy brackets beyond the threshold (2.5 GeV) are used. Also, dead or hot towers in ERT needn't necessarily occur because of the malfunctioning of the tower itself, but could be due to the trigger electronics malfunctioning in this region.
- Finally, we establish a “fiducial region” in each sector, excluding the towers on the edges (two rows and columns of towers), which are not allowed to be cluster centers. This is done in order to prevent forming clusters that may leak a substantial fraction of their energy from the calorimeter.

In this analysis, we not only remove the towers which have been identified as bad, but also a grid of 3*3 towers around this.

By this method, about 10% of all towers are removed from the analysis.

Sector	DeadWarn	Edges	Total excluded
0	195(7.52%)	432(16.7%)	20.02%
1	201(7.75%)	432(16.7%)	20.25%
2	263(10.14%)	432(16.7%)	22.64%
3	282(10.87%)	432(16.7%)	23.37%
4	151(5.85%)	432(16.7%)	18.32%
5	470(18.13%)	432(16.7%)	30.63%
6	1037(22.5%)	576(12.5%)	31.87%
7	1352(29.34%)	576(12.5%)	38.71%

Table 4.1: Fraction of dead/hot and edge towers in each sector.

Figure 4.2: One dimensional representation of number of hits in the towers in each sector before calibration in the energy range [0-30] GeV.

Figure 4.3: One dimensional representation of number of hits in the towers in each sector after calibration in the energy range $[0-30]$ GeV.

Figure 4.4: Two dimensional hit map for each sector after calibration. White areas are the regions excluded by the final dead/hot map, which is the union of the dead hot maps from MB and ERT in different energy bins, and its 3*3 towers masked it.

4.3.2 Timing Calibration

The calibration tables for this was obtained from Carlos Perez-Lara and Veronica Canoa Roman. The exact procedure is detailed in Analysis Note 1410. Their calibration was done with the central trigger. Due to unknown reasons, there was still a run dependence to mean TOF value for both MB and ERT trigger. In this analysis, the dependency was further corrected by including an additional run-dependent table. Note that according to PHENIX convention the TOF for photons is 0 (the collision vertex and impact-position dependent “flash time”, i.e. the expected flight time of the photon from the collision vertex to the impacted tower, is subtracted). This makes the timing cuts on photons much more simple and transparent.

Figure 4.5: Mean time of flight of photon candidates in each run in MB (left) and ERT (right) triggered data after calibration.

Figure 4.6: Sigma of time of flight of photon candidates in each run in MB (left) and ERT (right) triggered data after calibration.

4.3.3 List of good runs

Overall the run numbers for d+Au collision in 2016 are from 454774 to 455639. If there was no issue in recording data, detector issues or trigger related issues, every run should be identical to others, on average. Several runs were removed from the analysis due to various reasons. These are :

- No recorded run for ERT trigger : In this analysis, the normalization between MB and ERT is obtained from the number of runs recorded in each of them. Therefore we need to use the subset of runs which have both MB and ERT-triggered events. Five run numbers as indicated in the first row of Table 2 are excluded as they don't have any recorded ERT-triggered events.
- Stopped because run control server died: Although there is good data recorded in run number 455222, this run wasn't ended properly and thus has bad statistics like "scaledberraw" and "scaledberlive" and without it, the normalization constant can't be obtained. Reference : <https://phenix-intra.sdcc.bnl.gov/WWW/run/daq/runcontrol/RunSummary.php?RunNumber=455222>
- Crazy ERT scaledown : In runs 455344 and 455346, the ERT data is scaled down by a large number. This is tabulated in Appendix 1 in table 1 of PHENIX analysis note 1464 .
- Run control status failed : Although this is a good run, the run status isn't recorded correctly and without it, the normalization constant can't be obtained. Ref: <https://phenix-intra.sdcc.bnl.gov/WWW/run/daq/runcontrol/RunSummary.php?RunNumber=455590>
- Zero events in MB and ERT : In these runs, there are no runs that are saved during analysis. Figure 4 and Figure 5 shows the number of events in MB and ERT respectively.
- Sigma TOF : The sigma of the time of flight of all particles in a run is plotted in Fig. 10 and Fig. 11 for MB and ERT respectively. Run number 455352 is excluded as it has a large TOF width.

Outside of this, average number of clusters and mean time of flight for every run was also checked and plotted in Fig. 6 to Fig. 9.

Reason	Runs excluded
No recorded run for ERT trigger	455062, 455063, 455064, 455065, 455066
Run abruptly ended because the run control server died	455222
Low number of events due to crazy ERT scaledown	455344, 455346
Run control status failed	455590
Zero events (in MB & ERT)	455224, 455449
Sigma TOF	455352

Table 4.2: List of runs that are excluded from analysis and their reasons

(a) MB-triggered

(b) ERT-triggered

Figure 4.7: Total number of events in MB- and ERT-triggered runs

(a) MB-triggered

(b) ERT-triggered

Figure 4.8: Average number of gamma clusters per event as a function of run number in MB- and ERT-triggered runs

4.3.4 Quality cuts

In addition to all the calibration, we make the following cuts on the particle showers to make the photon sample cleaner for the analysis.

- χ^2 cut: A particle identification cut which is based on the shape of the shower produced by electromagnetic and hadronic particles is used in this analysis. This is defined as

$$\chi^2 = \sum_i \frac{(E_i^{meas} - E_i^{pred})^2}{\sigma_i^2} \quad (4.1)$$

where E_i^{meas} and E_i^{pred} are the measured and predicted energy deposit in the i -th tower and σ_i is the fluctuation in the predicted energy of EM showers. The predicted energy and its sigma are calculated from an energy-, impact point- and impact angle-dependent parameterization, obtained from test beam data taken with the towers of EMCal. A cut of $\chi^2 < 3.0$ has 90% efficiency in correctly identifying a true EM shower and 75% efficiency in rejecting a hadron shower.

- Energy threshold cut : Only photon showers above 0.3 GeV and below 30 GeV are used.
- Timing cut : A cut on the time of flight (TOF) of the showers in the EMCal helps reduce hadron contamination. The average sigma of photon showers in this analysis is 0.8 ns and a TOF cut of $< 3\sigma$ is applied. This $< 3\sigma$ cut is done for the sigma value of time of flight for each sector independently. This cut is also an effective tool in eliminating particles from overlapping events.
- Asymmetry cut : For π^0 extraction, only decay photons which pass the asymmetric cut $\frac{|E_1 - E_2|}{E_1 + E_2} < 0.8$ is included in the analysis.

4.4 Raw π^0 yield: MB and ERT-triggered dataset

Most of the photons detected in EMCal come from the decay of $\pi^0 \rightarrow \gamma\gamma$. So the first step in the analysis will be to reconstruct π^0 from photons, so that these can be removed as background from the direct photon analysis. Invariant mass reconstruction from decayed products is given by $M_{\gamma\gamma} = \sqrt{2E_1E_2(1 - \cos\phi)}$, where E_1 and E_2 is the energy of the two decay products and ϕ is the opening angle between them.

The method to obtain raw π^0 spectrum is broadly divided into two categories : (i) mixed event background subtraction and (ii) background subtraction based on average bin content outside the π^0 peak.

4.4.1 Mixed background subtraction

The procedure for mixed background subtraction is slightly different for MB and ERT-triggered events. The different steps are shown in different panels in Fig 12 and Fig 13.

- Panel 1: In a given event, all pairs of photons which belong to a sector are reconstructed to calculate the invariant mass and transverse momentum of the parent particle. These are then binned into different momentum and centrality classes.
- Panel 2: To subtract out the combinatorial background from panel 1's histogram, a mixed event invariant mass histogram is constructed by using the first photon from one event and second photon from another event. Each photon from an event is mixed with all photons from forty other events with the same centrality, vertex and reaction plane as the original event. For example, if event A has 10 photons, and event B has 15 photons, the pairs of photons combined are 10×15 . Each photon in event A is combined with every photon in event B. In the case of ERT trigger, the mixed events are reconstructed with an additional requirement ie., one and only one of the two photons used for the reconstruction should satisfy the ERT trigger condition.
- Panel 3: For MB-triggered events, the mixed background is now normalised to the real event by factor S defined as: $S = \frac{I_{1,Real} + I_{2,Real}}{I_{1,Mix} + I_{2,Mix}}$ where I_1 is the integral in the mass range [0.08 , 0.1] and I_2 is the Integral in the mass range [0.18, 0.28]. For ERT-triggered events, the mixed background histogram's shape does not predict the shape of the combinatorial background well. Because of this, the approach to normalization is different. First the real event histogram is divided by mixed event histogram. Then the π^0 and η peak in the window [0.1 - 0.2] and [0.490 - 0.610] respectively are suppressed. This histogram is fitted with a third degree polynomial and the mixed event histogram is normalised by this polynomial.
- Panel 4: Although most of the background is removed, there is still some residual which is removed by a polynomial fit.

- Panel 5: Last step of background subtraction by linear fit.
- Panel 6: π^0 is counted in the counting window of [0.1 -0.17]

Figure 4.9: Procedure for mixed background subtraction in MB-triggered events. This is the six panel canvas obtained for p_T range [2.5 - 3.0] in the 0-88% centrality bin. From top left to bottom right, the panels are : Real invariant mass histogram, mixed invariant mass histogram, Real - (normalised) * mixed, polynomial fit residual, linear fit residual and peak extraction window.

Figure 4.10: Procedure for mixed background subtraction in ERT-triggered events. This the six panel canvas obtained for p_T range [5.5 - 6.0] in the 0-88% centrality bin. From top left to bottom right, the panels are : Real invariant mass histogram, mixed invariant mass histogram, Real - (normalised) * mixed, polynomial fit residual, linear fit residual and peak extraction window.

4.4.2 Average count subtraction

When the statistics are really low, then the background is subtracted just as an average count subtraction in the window [0.25 - 0.35].

- Panel 1: Invariant mass is calculated from all pairs of photons detected by the EMCAL detector for each event, similar to panel 1 in section 4.1. Also the average count is calculated in the window [0.25 - 0.35].
- Panel 2: Subtracting the average count from every bin in the first histogram.

Figure 4.11: Procedure for average count subtraction in MB-triggered events. The above is the two panel canvas obtained for p_T range [7.5 - 8.0] in the 0-88% centrality bin. Left is the real invariant mass histogram and right average subtracted real histogram.

Figure 4.12: Procedure for average count subtraction in ERT-triggered events. The above is the two panel canvas obtained for p_T range [12.5 - 13.0] in the 0-88% centrality bin. Left is the real invariant mass histogram and right average subtracted real histogram.

4.4.3 Centrality binned raw π^0 spectrum

From this absolute count of π^0 obtained from each p_T window, for different sectors, trigger condition and centrality of the raw yield is obtained by normalising to bin width (dp_T), rapidity window (dy) and total number of events in each centrality (N_{events}). The total number of events is obtained from MB trigger data set. For ERT data, this is multiplied by the scale down factor.

Figure 4.13: Centrality binned raw π^0 spectrum from MB- and ERT-triggered dataset for $\chi^2 < 3.0$ and $TOF < 3\sigma$ from PbSc detector.

(see section 4.4 for detailed explanation) For the selection of runs that are used in this analysis, the normalization factor is 513.46 (Appendix A, Table 2, PHENIX Analysis Note 1463).

4.4.4 Merging MB and ERT spectrum

The raw π^0 spectrum from BBCL1(> 0 tubes) narrowvtx (referred to as MB trigger) and ERT-triggered dataset need to be merged into a single continuous spectrum.

There are several methods to merge different datasets. The most common way to do this is to fit the ratio of raw π^0 spectrum from both the MB and ERT data set in the overlap region (5-8 GeV). This fit is used to normalise one data set with respect to another. In the 2016 d+Au data set, there wasn't enough statistics to implement the above method. In this analysis, the normalization factor is obtained from the effective scaledown factor for each trigger.

In PHENIX analysis note 1463, Appendix A, table 2 and table 3 lists the number of events that satisfied MB and ERT-4x4b trigger respectively for each run number. This is listed under the column name “scalerberlive”. The number of events that are stored after the scaledown is tabulated under the name “scalerberscaled”.

For instance, in run number 454774, the scaledown number of MB is 14285 and ERT4x4b is 0. What this means is only one in 14286 events that satisfy the MB trigger condition is saved whereas every event which satisfied the

ERT4x4b is saved. Typically, the rarer the event, the smaller the scaledown value as you want to capture all rare events.

Using this table, an effective scaledown is obtained. This is done by dividing the total number of events in column “scalerberlive” by total number of events in “scalerberscaled”.

The MB and ERT are drawn on the same plot, and we pick a transition p_T , below which we use the yield from MB dataset, and above which, we use from the ERT dataset. In this analysis, despite these efforts, the normalization factor isn’t exact. So a second step normalization is done after comparing the correct π^0 spectrum with already published data. This second normalization is then used to bootstrap the MB and ERT dataset of raw π^0 spectrum.

Figure 4.14: Flowchart of the two stages of normalization that is done in the process of merging MB and ERT-triggered spectrum

Figure 4.15: raw π^0 from MB and ERT spectrum in [0-88]% centrality after normalizing with the first normalization factor obtained by calculating the effective normalization factor. Left of blue dotted line are points from MB and right of blue dotted line are points from ERT dataset.

Figure 4.16: Comparing the corrected π^0 spectrum from this analysis with corrected spectrum obtained with Run 8 d+Au data by Norbert Novitzky. This is used to obtain a second normalization and correct the raw π^0 spectrum further. The legend here shows the value of fitted function in low p_T and high p_T after first and second normalization for all centrality.

Figure 4.17: raw π^0 from MB and ERT spectrum in [0-88]% centrality after re-normalizing with the second normalization factor by bootstrapping to Norbert's AN. Left of blue dotted line are points from MB and right of blue dotted line are points from ERT dataset.

Figure 4.18: Centrality binned raw π^0 spectrum from combined MB and ERT dataset for $\chi^2 < 3.0$ and $TOF < 3\sigma$ from PbSc detector.

4.5 Simulation - basic procedure

In this analysis, simulation is used for the following purposes.

- Correct raw π^0 spectrum
- Obtain decay gammas from corrected π^0 spectrum
- Estimate decay gammas from corrected η mesons
- Correct Direct Photon Spectrum.

Note that in traditional analyses, the raw inclusive photon spectrum is corrected first (into a “true” inclusive photon spectrum), then the “true” hadron decay gamma spectrum is subtracted in order to get the (corrected) direct photon spectrum. Recognizing that the raw inclusive photon spectrum is an – initially unknown – combination of direct and decay photons, and realizing that the response of the detector is different to single (direct) photons and correlated (decay) photons, particularly at higher p_T (merging, wrong energy sharing between adjacent clusters) our procedure is different. Instead of trying to correct the entire raw inclusive photon spectrum (where “raw” means “as measured in the detector”, and includes all effects from detector response, clustering algorithm, PID cuts, acceptance, etc.), using the simulation and the “true” (corrected) hadron spectra we calculate what would be the “raw” photon distribution seen in the detector that’s due solely to hadron decays. This raw decay photon distribution is then subtracted from the raw inclusive photon spectrum (which itself is modified to account for hadron contamination), and the remainder is the raw direct photon spectrum, which in turn is corrected with the simulated response to single (non-correlated) photons. Simulation is used in this analysis to correct for detector acceptance, efficiency and for smearing effects. Each of these will be explained in detail using π^0 and its decay gammas as reference. .

- **Detector Acceptance:** Not all decay gammas are reconstructed into π^0 s. Here are few reasons that this could happen
 - the EMCal detector covers only +/-0.35 in rapidity. So a significant portion of generated π^0 miss the detector.
 - Not all of the towers of the EMCal work properly during a run. Bad towers (Dead, Warm and Hot) are removed from the analysis as discussed in section 4.1.

- Only π^0 s with both the decay gammas within the same sector are reconstructed. While this leads to some loss of acceptance at low p_T , it improves the signal/background ratio significantly, making the π^0 yield extraction easier and more accurate.

- **Efficiency**

- The identification of photons in EMCal is argely based on the shower-shape and its comparison to the expected shape of electromagnetic showers. However, the clustering algorithm doesn't always work perfectly, nor does the shower shape model account for all possible, natural fluctuations. (This, as with any algorithm, can always lead to misidentification of a shower as a photon or exclusion of a true photon shower.)
- At high p_T , the decay gammas have really small opening angles and this can lead to merging of clusters, i.e. two gammas are reconstructed as single gammas. Moreover, even if the algorithm recognizes the two overlapping showers as separate, the energy sharing between them and/or the determination of the impact positions can be wrong.
- At high p_T , the photon clusters can sometime break up and thus be reconstructed as two different photons.

- **Smearing**

- Sometime the momentum of photon is mis-measured. This can lead to mis-measurement of π^0 invariant mass and momentum, a natural consequence of the finite resolution of the detector.

To correct for the above effects, PISA simulation with unfolding procedure is used.

A typical simulation chain is detailed as below using π^0 as an example. Similar simulation chain is done for Eta mesons and single photons.

4.5.1 Generating Input File

Input parameters in Oscar format are generated and fed to PISA, the PHENIX simulation software. Each parameter of an event in the simulation is randomly chosen from the following functions.

- Rapidity values are generated in $[-0.5, 0.5]$ window with a Gaussian probability distribution with mean and sigma as 0 and 10 respectively.

Figure 4.19: Distributions generated by random numbers for each of the primary parameters

- p_T is obtained as a uniform random distribution in the range $[0,30]$.
- Phi is a uniform random distribution in the range $[-\pi, \pi]$
- Vertex for an event is chosen to be identical (but for smearing effects) as that of the collision data in which this simulated π^0 is embedded.

Using the above parameters and mass of π^0 , secondary parameters like p_x, p_y, p_z and Energy are derived. A text file is created with these secondary parameters and positions $x=0, y=0, z = \text{vertex}$ and $t=0$.

4.5.2 PISA

PISA processes these single π^0 events and handles the decay mechanism and its interaction with various detector subsystems. The energy deposited by the decay photons in the EMCal detector and their impact point is the primary information that is needed from this step.

After processing through PISA, pisaToDST is used to reconstruct the tracks and clusters similar to the reconstruction algorithm used in the data analysis.

4.5.3 Embedding

In heavy ion collision, due to large multiplicity, there are underlying event signatures which cannot be realistically obtained in any simulation software.

To mimic a real event, the clusters from the simulated event are declusterized and the energy deposited in the EMCal towers in the simulated event is merged with tower energies from a real event. This merged tower energy is then clusterized again by usual PHENIX algorithms. In the process, information whether a tower has energy contributed from the simulated event, and if so, properties of the original simulated particle are preserved for evaluation purposes.

Scaling and smearing the detector response

In PISA simulation, the detector is assumed to be ideal (in the sense that the “gains” of the towers are perfectly balanced and the resolution corresponds to the *nominal* resolution measured in the test-beam with single particles) and this needs to be corrected for by comparing the simulated data with the real data. The peak position and the width of the π^0 which is obtained from the invariant mass reconstruction from cluster pair energies in simulation and data are compared. The ratio from the mean and width are fed as scaling and smearing factor to the simulation to make the detector response in PISA similar to real event (*in situ* resolution). Although the π^0 is simulated in (0-30 GeV) range, for this step alone, it is simulated only in the (0-10 GeV) range as the shape of the PbGl detector response itself was very different from the simulation response when I simulate 0-30 GeV pions, which made it hard to correct this with one scaling and smearing factor. This is shown in Fig.4.20.

4.5.4 TTree

The information from the embedding event is stored into TTree which are used in the analysis. Various layers of information is available at the end of this step.

- Event level information :This gives us “true” information about the event like Vertex, number of cluster, trigger bit, generated p_T generated momentum of π^0 , asymmetry in the energy of decay photons etc
- Cluster level information: Information from tracks and clusters in the EMCal that are experimentally available from the data : Energy deposited, PID, Number of tracks, ancestry level of tracks etc.
- Reconstruction level information: Information obtained from cluster pairs like Invariant mass, reconstructed p_T of the reconstructed π^0 , asymmetry in energy deposited by cluster pairs

(a) Mean π^0 peak

(b) Width π^0 peak

Figure 4.20: Ratio of mean and width of π^0 peak from data and simulation after energy calibration in PbSc detector.

With all this information, we use the method of unfolding with response matrix to obtain our corrected spectrum from raw spectrum.

4.5.5 Cuts and calibration in simulation

All quality cuts (except timing cut) that were used in the data as described in section 4.4, are also applied exactly in the simulation.

Timing cut in simulation

The timing signal of the EMCal is properly simulated for testbeam data (ideal circumstances), but imperfections due to the readout electronics are not, so the simulated TOF can not be easily used for PID purposes. Instead, we use and empirically established “timing deadmap”. This deadmap is a list of all the towers, whose sigma is very different from the average sigma of EMCal towers. All towers with mean TOF $> 1ns$ and sigma TOF $> 1.47ns$ are flagged and removed as a deadmap in the simulation. No further 3x3 mask is applied to these towers.

4.6 Response Matrix

The response matrix describes the probability that a true value x is reconstructed at value y , where y belongs to the set of all possibilities.

4.6.1 Correcting raw π^0 spectrum

The p_T of the π^0 that is measured can be different from its generated p_T . This could happen due to any of the reasons mentioned in section 6. The raw yield spectrum obtained needs to be corrected for these effects. This can be done by a one step process of generating a response matrix of π^0 momentum.

Obtaining π^0 momentum response matrix

For every event, the generated and the measured p_T of the π^0 is recorded. With this information, a two dimensional matrix is created with the x axis as the generated p_T and the y axis as measured or reconstructed p_T . By running large simulation statistics, this 2D matrix is built. Note that while building it, the actual cuts used in the analysis are applied (i.e. the response matrix differs for different analysis cuts). This matrix is then normalised by dividing every column by the number of π^0 generated in that p_T bin, making its elements a probability, that a π^0 with true $p_T=x$ was actually reconstructed (passing the analysis cuts and the invariant mass being in the π^0 range), but with $p_T=y$. This takes care in one single step of the acceptance, reconstruction efficiency and energy smearing.

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_{11} & x_{12} & \dots & x_{1n} \\ x_{21} & x_{22} & \dots & x_{2n} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot \\ x_{m1} & x_{m2} & \dots & x_{mn} \end{bmatrix} \text{elements divided with } [n_1 \quad n_2 \quad \dots \quad n_n] \longrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} \frac{x_{11}}{n_1} & \frac{x_{12}}{n_2} & \dots & \frac{x_{1n}}{n_n} \\ \frac{x_{21}}{n_1} & \frac{x_{22}}{n_2} & \dots & \frac{x_{2n}}{n_n} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot \\ \frac{x_{m1}}{n_1} & \frac{x_{m2}}{n_2} & \dots & \frac{x_{mn}}{n_n} \end{bmatrix}$$

In the above (left) matrix, element x_{ij} is the number of events where the generated p_T of the π^0 is i but was reconstructed as j . The vector in the middle represents the number of π^0 in each p_T bin. Dividing each p_T bin column in the matrix by the number of elements gives the response matrix.

Figure 4.21: Left: Two dimensional matrix of generated π^0 p_T vs measured π^0 p_T . Middle: Number of π^0 generated in each p_T bin. Right: Response Matrix of π^0 p_T .

True spectrum from measured spectrum

Consider a True Spectrum denoted by vector T and response matrix denoted by R . The measured spectrum O would be the convolution of the vector T and matrix R .

$$T * R = O \quad (4.2)$$

To obtain the true spectrum from the measured spectrum, the matrix R should in principle be inverted. However, the inverse is notoriously unstable, due to the small, fluctuating off-diagonal elements. Various techniques exist for the “regularization” of the response matrix, but we found the following method more straightforward and physics-wise justified. Our only (implicit) assumption on the true spectrum is that it is a smooth function with a slowly varying derivative. As for the data points, their point-by-point fluctuations should be dominated by statistics (but large overall distortions, for instance due to acceptance varying strongly with p_T are allowed).

Start with a trial function T_1 , typically a fit to a spectrum already measured in a similar collision system, which when convoluted with M gives O_1 . Compare O_1 with the measured raw yield and obtain the ratio of them as a function of p_T . The trial function is multiplied with the ratio. This will be the new starting value. With multiple iterations, the spectrum converges to the measured spectrum.

Figure 4.22: Trial function convoluted with response matrix and the result is compared with the spectrum from the data.

$$\frac{\begin{bmatrix} M \end{bmatrix}}{\begin{bmatrix} O \end{bmatrix}} \equiv \begin{bmatrix} M_1/O_1 \\ M_2/O_2 \\ \vdots \\ M_n/O_n \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} R_{11} & R_{21} & \dots & R_{n1} \\ R_{12} & \dots & \dots & \\ \vdots & & & \\ R_{1n} & & & R_{nn} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} M_1/O_1 T_1 \\ M_2/O_2 T_2 \\ \vdots \\ M_n/O_n T_n \end{bmatrix} \equiv \begin{bmatrix} O'_1 \\ O'_2 \\ \vdots \\ O'_n \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 4.23: after comparison, the ratio is obtained and the initial trial function is modified accordingly and new convoluted vector is obtained.

For π^0 , the initial trial function (T) is obtained by fitting previously published data (AN590) with Hagedorn function. To obtain a stable response matrix is a statistics heavy process and thus about 200 million events with single π^0 s were simulated.

Figure 4.24: Top left: Red is the initial trial function. Blue is the modified vector after 5 iterations with variable binning which matches the raw data binning. Top right: Response matrix of π^0 momentum. Bottom left: Red is the raw π^0 spectrum. Grey is the convolution of trial vector with the response matrix. Bottom Right: ratio of grey points from previous panel by the red points.

This is done for all centralities to obtain centrality binned corrected π^0 spectrum. In this step, error bars aren't calculated as it is hard to propagate raw π^0 error onto corrected π^0 directly due to the multiple iterations involving matrix multiplication.

As evident from the top left plot of Fig. 4.24, there is still a small kink in the corrected spectrum around 6.5 GeV. This is due to residual normalization error in matching MB and ERT-triggered data set and the method of unfolding with response matrix causes mismatch in the neighbouring points around the transition region. Systematic error from this is studied in section [number](#).

Figure 4.25: Centrality binned corrected π^0 spectrum of combined MB and ERT for $\chi^2 < 3.0$ and $TOF < 3\sigma$ from PbSc detector. The error bars shown in this are only approximate estimate. Exact statistical and systematic errors are calculated in section 4.12 and 4.13

4.6.2 Obtaining decay gamma spectrum from corrected π^0 spectrum

Using the same simulation chain, another matrix is created. This is a response matrix for decay gammas from the corrected π^0 spectrum (but not the invariant yield!) The x-axis of matrix is the generated p_T of the π^0 and the y-axis is the energy deposited by the two decay gammas. For each event (one π^0 per event), zero to n entries are made depending on how many gammas, e^+ , e^- from dalits and conversion pairs, π^+ , π^- etc reached the detector and passed the PID cuts. This matrix, similar to the π^0 response matrix, is normalised by the number of π^0 generated in a given p_T bin. The procedure is illustrated in Fig. 4.26. Note that the response matrix is generated in narrow bins over the entire p_T range, but the data points are shown in wider bins at high p_T due to lack of statistics. For the unfolding these data points are artificially redistributed in the narrow bins corresponding to the response matrix, according to the overall slope, which causes the strange jumps of the points at high p_T .

Figure 4.26: Obtaining raw decay gamma spectrum of π^0 using the method of unfolding with response matrix. Left Panel: corrected π^0 spectrum. Center Panel: normalised decay gamma response matrix. Right panel: decay gamma spectrum.

Figure 4.27: Centrality binned raw decay gamma from corrected π^0 spectrum for $\chi^2 < 3.0$ and $TOF < 3\sigma$ from PbSc detector. The error bars shown in this are only approximate estimate. Exact statistical and systematic errors are calculated in section 4.12 and 4.13

4.6.3 Corrected η spectrum using η/π^0 ratio

In this analysis, we do not have enough statistics to obtain an η spectrum. So a corrected η spectrum is obtained using global fits to η/π^0 ratio.

Figure 4.28: Global fits to η/π^0 ratio in Au+Au collisions using the method of gaussian process regression (GPR) [41].

Figure 4.29: Centrality binned corrected η spectrum from corrected π^0 spectrum for $\chi^2 < 3.0$ and $TOF < 3\sigma$ from PbSc detector. The error bars shown in this are only approximate estimate. Exact statistical and systematic errors are calculated in section 4.12 and 4.13.

4.6.4 Obtaining decay gamma spectrum from corrected η spectrum

This is done similar to section 7.2 but with η simulations. Eta mesons have several decay channels including, $\eta \rightarrow 2\gamma$ (39.41%), $\eta \rightarrow 3\pi^0$ (32.68%), $\eta \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ (22.92%), $\eta \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\gamma$ (4.22%) etc. In the η/π^0 ratio, the π^0 includes those created in a heavy ion collision and those obtained from decays of other heavier mesons like η, Ω etc. In experimental measurement of η spectrum, the spectra is obtained from the $\eta \rightarrow 2\gamma$ decay channel and scaled up by the branching ratio of this decay channel.

To avoid over counting of decay gammas from η mesons, the Eta simulation has a cut on ancestry level. This restricts the response matrix to exclude the $\eta \rightarrow 3\pi^0$ by ignoring photons from the second ancestry level and conversion pairs of e^+/e^- from the third ancestry level. This is then normalised by the total number of Etas generated in each p_T bin.

Once the response matrix is generated, the decay gammas from the η s are calculated by similar procedure as explained in Section 4.6.2.

Figure 4.30: Obtaining raw decay gamma spectrum of η using the method of unfolding with response matrix. Left Panel: corrected η spectrum. Center Panel: normalised decay gamma response matrix. Right panel: decay gamma spectrum.

4.6.5 Decay gammas from Ω, η'

Using fast simulation, we estimate this correction factor to be 1.191.

Figure 4.31: Centrality binned raw decay spectrum of corrected η spectrum for $\chi^2 < 3.0$ and $TOF < 3\sigma$. The error bars shown in this are only approximate estimate. Exact statistical and systematic errors are calculated in section 4.12 and 4.13.

4.7 Understanding merging of decay hadron clusters

In a typical low p_T analysis of direct photon, the raw π^0 spectrum is corrected using simulations and the decay gamma (γ^{π^0}) from this is obtained purely by boost kinematics of $1 \rightarrow 2$ particle decay mechanism. The decay gamma from other hadrons like η, Ω, η' etc are obtained using “cocktail ratio” correction to γ^{π^0} .

In a high p_T analysis, although the same procedure is often followed, strictly speaking, this isn't correct. The effects we discuss below depend on two main parameters, the mass of the parent particle and its p_T .

In their rest frame π^0 s decay isotropically into two, back-to-back photons of equal energy (about 70 MeV). However, when boosted, the decay photon distributions become anisotropic, peaked in the boost direction, and the energy of the two photons will be different (“asymmetric decay”), except when the plane of the decay in the π^0 rest frame is orthogonal to the boost direction (“symmetric decays”). In the lab frame we define the asymmetry as $\alpha = (|E_{\gamma_1} - E_{\gamma_2}|)/(E_{\gamma_1} + E_{\gamma_2})$. The smallest possible opening angle between the two photons is reached for $\alpha = 0$ symmetric decays. As we move up in p_T (boost), the minimum opening angle decreases, and at some point the two photon clusters get too close to each other to be unambiguously resolved. That raises two kind of problems. At first the clusters start overlapping, but only partially: the clustering algorithm recognizes them as two photons, and has to share the energy deposited in the overlap region. This energy sharing will be sometimes imperfect: one cluster will be assigned higher energy, than the corresponding true photon, the other smaller. This is a serious problem (see below). Also, as the photons move even closer, at some point the algorithm will find only one cluster (merging). This means that the corresponding π^0 will be unmeasurable (at least with the usual invariant mass reconstruction): it is lost. Worst still, it might be mistaken for a *single* photon carrying the entire energy of the π^0 . Now, since the true direct photon spectra decrease with a high power of p_T , having even a few fake high p_T photons can seriously compromise the measurement (photons pushed to lower p_T are also a problem, but a smaller one, since there the true yield is more abundant, i.e. the error caused by the false additional entries is smaller).

Let's first examine the problem of wrong energy sharing. How can it be recognized? Kinematically, and considering the full solid angle, for any fixed $\pi^0 p_T$ the distribution of the decay γ energies should be flat (from 0 to the full $\pi^0 p_T$). Detector properties, acceptance and the clustering algorithm modifies it somewhat (in particular, enhancing very low energies), but at high enough

parent p_T most of the distribution should be uniform, even in our limited acceptance (due to the fact that for boosted π^0 the decay photons are strongly focused around the boost direction). In Fig. 4.32 the decay photon distributions are shown for four different parent π^0 momenta. As we can see, up to 10 GeV/ c the distribution is essentially flat in decay photon p_T (the tail is due to detector resolution). However, at 15 GeV/ c there is a notable deficit at medium p_T and an excess near the highest p_T values as well as enhancement at low p_T . The effect is even more dramatic at 20 GeV/ c (note that the y scale is logarithmic). The explanation is simple: the medium- p_T region is filled by decay γ from symmetric decays, which in turn have the smallest opening angle, therefore, cluster merging makes them disappear first. On the other hand, if a small and a high energy photon get close, but still remain distinguishable, the energy sharing algorithm tends to pull energy from the lower energy photon ($E_{meas} < E_{true}$), and assign it to the higher energy photon ($E_{meas} > E_{true}$). This artificially *enhances* the observed photon yield at high p_T (and at very low p_T , but that's less of an issue), and *depletes* it at medium p_T . Finally, note that the two-gamma distributions per construction also include the cases when the two photons merged into only one cluster, but the actual particle identification still accepted it as a photon candidate. The effect is further proven by Fig. 4.33, where the same distributions for η are shown. Since the η has three times the mass of the π^0 , their decay photons don't get close in this kinematic range, so all two-gamma distributions are flat.

The simulation captures these two phenomenon well.¹ As it can be seen in Fig.4.32 and Fig. 4.33, the shape of the raw decay gamma spectrum from π^0 (γ^{π^0}) and η (γ^η) are very different at high p_T . This implies that the γ^η is not just $C^*(\gamma^{\pi^0})$, where C is a constant. The two photons from π^0 start to merge at a lower p_T than those of η . In fact, for the p_T range considered in this thesis, the decay gammas from η are always well separated. Decay gamma from Ω and η' , which are heavier hadrons than η , will also not merge in the p_T range of interest and thus can be estimated by just a multiplicative factor to the γ^η as done in Sec.4.6.5.

Now it is clear why we claim that at sufficiently high p_T the traditional way to analyze photons is not correct. The traditional analysis goes like this: (1) An inclusive raw γ spectrum is measured. (2) Using (single!) photon simulations from this a "fully corrected inclusive" photon spectrum is produced. (3) Using (fully corrected) π^0 spectra the number of expected decay photons is calculated, from simple decay kinematics. (4) Decay photons from other hadrons are estimated and added. (5) The decay photons are subtracted from

¹There is a systematic error arising from how well the simulation captures this effect, but this is discussed in Sec. 4.13.

the “fully corrected” inclusive photons, resulting in the direct photon spectrum.

As it is clear from the previous paragraphs, the problem is with step (2) above. The response of the detector to random, single photons is different from the response to the *correlated* decay photons (at higher p_T), and they need a different correction! ² The raw inclusive photon spectrum is *an initially unknown mixture* of single photons (to be corrected one way) and decay photons (to be corrected another way). Since we don’t know the ratio of the two components in the mixture (finding it is essentially the direct photon measurement itself!), there is no way to properly correct the raw inclusive photon spectrum in one step *as soon as wrong energy sharing and cluster merging starts playing a role*. This last remark also explains why the problem hasn’t been recognized and addressed earlier: it arises only at relatively high p_T , mostly beyond the reach of earlier experiments. Note that what “relatively high p_T ” is depends on the actual detector, it’s granularity, Moliere-radius, distance from the vertex, etc. For instance, in PHENIX proper wrong energy sharing / merging starts earlier in PbSc than in PbGl.

Figure 4.32: Two gamma decay distribution of π^0 s at different p_T in the PbSc.

Let’s discuss now the problem of merging, i.e. loss of π^0 s measured at high p_T . The amount of loss can only be derived from simulations, so it is crucial to

²To put it simply: π^0 s do not just decay into two photons, they decay into two *correlated* photons, and this has consequences in an actual measurement.

Figure 4.33: Two gamma decay distribution of η s at different p_T in the PbSc.

make sure that it indeed describes even the fine details of overlapping clusters. Fortunately, there is a simple, data-driven way to test the simulations. For boosted π^0 s in 4π all asymmetries $\alpha = (|E_{\gamma_1} - E_{\gamma_2}|)/(E_{\gamma_1} + E_{\gamma_2})$ are equally probable. At higher p_T - due to forward focusing - this becomes essentially true even in our limited acceptance. We know, that the most symmetric ($\alpha \approx 0$) decays have the smallest opening angle, so they will be first affected by merging, and the most asymmetric ones will be affected last (i.e. at highest p_T). We can then extract the raw π^0 yields as a function of p_T in smaller bins of asymmetry, say $0.0 \leq \alpha < 0.2$, $0.2 \leq \alpha < 0.4$, etc., and normalize these yields with the cumulated yield observed at all asymmetries ($0.0 \leq \alpha < 0.95$). As long as there is no merging, we expect the relative yields to be equal in all asymmetry bin. As soon as merging starts, the relative yield from the lowest asymmetry bin should go down, and the significance of higher asymmetry bins should increase. We can then repeat the same procedure with simulations, and compare, how do the raw relative yields change with asymmetry and p_T . Clearly the shape of the curves very strongly depends on how well the simulation describes the subtle details of cluster merging. The answer can be seen in Fig. 4.34. The data used are from the Run-9 500 GeV $p+p$ run because it has higher p_T reach and better statistics. Within statistical uncertainties the measured points are perfectly described by the simulation curves (smooth, since not limited by statistics). This indicates that the simulation describes very well even the fine details of cluster merging.

Figure 4.34: Fraction of reconstructable π^0 s in the PbSc at the given p_T in different asymmetry bins in p+p collisions at 500GeV. Points are data, smooth curves are simulation (not limited by statistics). The near-perfect agreement gives us confidence that the simulation handles close-by and merged clusters properly.

4.8 Inclusive photon spectrum

This is a spectrum of all photons that are deposited in the EMCal. They have the same particle identification and timing cuts as π^0 spectrum. This spectrum is obtained independently for MB and ERT and their normalization matched by the constant obtained in section 4.4.4. This is shown in Fig. 4.35 and the merged spectrum in Fig.4.36.

4.8.1 Hadron contamination

To get an estimate of Hadron contamination at low p_T , we ran PYTHIA full event simulation for p+p collisions and passed the output of this through PISA. The output of this gives us cluster level information at the EMCal, to which, we applied cuts that are used in this analysis ($\chi^2 < 3.0$, energy threshold > 0.3 , TOF $< 5ns$). In Fig. 4.37, we present the ratio of the number of clusters which are from hadrons and crossed the cuts mentioned above over total number of clusters which crossed the cuts defined here as the Hadron contamination factor ($R(p_T)$). The inclusive photon is modified by a factor of

Figure 4.35: Raw inclusive photon spectrum from MB and ERT in [0-88]% centrality after renormalizing with the second normalization factor by bootstrapping to Norbert's AN. Left of blue dotted line are points from MB and right of blue dotted line are points from ERT dataset.

$(1 - R(p_T))$ to account for this effect.

Figure 4.36: Centrality binned raw inclusive gamma spectrum from combined MB and ERT dataset for $\chi^2 < 3.0$ and $TOF < 3\sigma$ from PbSc detector. The error bars shown in this are only approximate estimate. Exact statistical and systematic errors are calculated in section 4.12 and 4.13.

Notes on spectra at low p_T

In any photon analysis relying solely on *electromagnetic* calorimeter information, at low p_T the contamination from hadrons is a major problem. Photons and electrons deposit essentially all their energy in the EMCal (with a characteristic average showershape), so at mid-rapidity the measured cluster energy and the p_T of the particle are about the same. Barring malfunctions of the clustering algorithm high p_T photons don't contribute to the low p_T part of the spectrum (and if they do, the simulation reproduces this well, since electromagnetic showers are almost perfectly simulated in GEANT for decades).

The situation is quite different for hadrons. Since the EMCal is only about one nuclear interaction length deep, most hadrons don't get stopped in it, in fact, many of them (some 30-40%) don't even start a nuclear interaction, just deposit energy by dE/dx (usually "minimum ionizing"). Even for those that

start a hadronic shower, most of the shower energy is “leaked out” at the end of the calorimeter. While the produced shower has typically a different shape from the electromagnetic ones, natural fluctuations make a *clean* separation (based on shower shape) from the e.m. showers impossible. In addition, hadron showers are not as well reproduced in GEANT3 (FLUKA) as electromagnetic ones, so the contamination can not be precisely simulated. Even worse, in the 1-2 GeV region antiprotons and antineutrons, even if very low p_T , can stop and annihilate, adding a sizeable fake signal.

The net result is, that if one measures a 4 GeV cluster, that shower-shape-wise looks like a photon, there are two possibilities. Either it is indeed electromagnetic, and then its true p_T is indeed close to 4 GeV/c (modulo resolution and accidental overlaps), or it is a hadron mimicking a photon and of *any* p_T higher than 4 GeV/c, since *in the photon measurement only the energy actually deposited counts, not the p_T* . That means that *all* hadrons of sufficiently high p_T can contaminate the low p_T photon measurement by depositing part of their energy in the EMCal.

Fortunately, the very same effect works in favor of the high p_T photon measurement. Since the EMCal is only about one nuclear interaction length deep, and depositing all hadronic energy would need 3-8 interaction lengths, a sufficiently high energy cluster is virtually certain to be of electromagnetic origin, not hadronic.

That’s why we feel justified to treat the lower p_T (up to 5-6 GeV/c) and the higher p_T part fundamentally differently. While in the first case the effects of the hadron contamination are still under intense study, we feel that at higher p_T the results are quite solid (up to the point where cluster merging from close-by decay photons becomes overwhelming).

Figure 4.37: Plotted here is fraction of clusters which satisfy the quality cuts like $\chi^2 < 3.0$ and energy threshold cut but are not true electromagnetic shower.

4.9 Direct photon spectrum

The raw direct photon spectrum is obtained by,

$$\gamma^{direct} = \gamma^{incl}(1 - R(p_T)) - \gamma^{\pi^0} - 1.191 * \gamma^\eta \quad (4.3)$$

where γ^{incl} is the raw inclusive gamma spectrum from Sec., $R(p_T)$ is the hadron contamination factor discussed in Sec. 4.8.1. γ^{π^0} and γ^η are the decay gamma spectrum from π^0 s and η s respectively as discussed in Sec.4.6.2 and 4.6.4. The factor ‘1.191’ is correction to γ^η include corrections from other heavy hadrons like Ω and η' .

In this equation, all the photons mentioned are *raw*, meaning they are what is observed or expected to be observed in our detector setup. This raw direct photon spectrum is then corrected using a separate single photon simulation.

Similar to the π^0 s, the raw direct photon spectrum is corrected using a single photon simulation by the method of iterative unfolding with a response matrix as described in Section 4.6.

Figure 4.38: Top left: Red is the initial trial function. Blue is the modified vector after 5 iterations with variable binning which matches the raw data binning. Top right: Response matrix of π^0 momentum. Bottom left: Red is the raw π^0 spectrum. Grey is the convolution of trial vector with the response matrix. Bottom Right: ratio of grey points from previous panel by the red points.

Figure 4.39: Centrality binned corrected direct photon spectrum from combined MB and ERT dataset for $\chi^2 < 3.0$ and $TOF < 3\sigma$ from PbSc detector. The error bars shown in this are only approximate estimate. Exact statistical and systematic errors are calculated in section 4.12 and 4.13.

4.10 Summary of section 4.4 to section 4.9

Figure 4.40: Schematic diagram describing Section 5 to Section 13. $S1_M1$ indicates the π^0 response matrix. $S1_M2$ indicates the decay gamma response matrix of π^0 . YR's ratio is Yuanjie Ren's ratio as mentioned in Section 8 and $S2_M2$ indicates the decay gamma response matrix of η . $S3_M1$ indicates the response matrix of direct γ .

4.11 Derived plots

From the above analysis, we obtain these plots to make our physics message obvious. All of these plots are plotted in four different bins of centrality for high p_T (>7 GeV).

- Single Ratio: Ratio of corrected direct γ over corrected π^0 .
- Double Ratio The above ratio at different centralities divided by the minimum bias single ratio.
- $R_{dAu}^{\pi^0}$: Nuclear modification factor as defined in Eq.5.3 obtained for π^0 s.

- R_{dAu}^γ : Nuclear modification factor as defined in Eq. 5.3 obtained for direct photons.
- Modified $R_{dAu}^{\pi^0}$: The $R_{dAu}^{\pi^0}$ is divided by the R_{dAu}^γ . This gives modified $R_{dAu}^{\pi^0}$ which is independent of N_{coll} calculated by Glauber model.

These are plotted along with their corresponding statistical and systematic errors from Fig.5.1a to 5.11b

4.12 Statistical Error

In this analysis, it is not straightforward to obtain statistical errors as the method of iterative unfolding with the response matrix makes it cumbersome to propagate the error from a raw spectrum to a corrected spectrum. Thus, a sampling method is utilised to obtain statistical error for the corrected spectrum.

4.12.1 Procedure for obtaining error through sampling method

Let us consider each p_T point in a raw spectrum with its error bars as $x_1 \pm e_1$, $x_2 \pm e_2$, $x_3 \pm e_3$, $x_n \pm e_n$.

- Using the central value of raw spectrum $x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n$ and the method of unfolding procedure described in Section 4.6, the central value of corrected spectrum $y_1, y_2, y_3, \dots, y_n$ is obtained.
- Create a Gaussian function for each p_T point of raw spectrum with the mean being the central value and sigma being error value.
- Get a new raw spectrum by extracting a random value from the Gaussian distribution at each p_T point: $x'_1, x'_2, x'_3 \dots x'_n$. Using this as the new input spectrum, obtain the corresponding corrected spectrum $y'_1, y'_2, y'_3 \dots y'_n$. This is then repeated 4000 times.
- Each p_T point in the corrected spectrum now has a Gaussian spread around it. The sigma of the Gaussian is the error value of that point.

4.12.2 Sampling method applied to this analysis

To understand how statistical errors are obtained for each of the spectra in this analysis, it's important to understand the three independent chains that this analysis has.

Chain 1: Starting with raw π^0 spectrum, we obtain corrected π^0 spectrum, corrected η spectrum, raw decay photons from π^0 s and η s. The method of sampling as mentioned in section 4.12.1 is done for this entire chain 4000 times. This gives error on each p_T point, for each spectrum and for their different centralities.

Chain 2: From the decay photons from above and raw inclusive photon, obtain raw direct photon spectrum. As this step involves only straightforward addition and subtraction of spectra, the error is propagated by traditional methods.

Chain 3: Starting with raw direct photons, obtaining corrected direct photon. Another chain of sampling errors is done here to obtain errors on the corrected direct photon spectrum from the error on raw direct photon spectrum for each centrality.

Chain 4: The statistical error for the plots mentioned in section: 4.11 is obtained by the straightforward method of error propagation when variables with errors are divided.

Figure 4.41: Gaussian distribution at different p_T points in raw π^0 spectrum in centrality [0 - 20] %. These histograms are used to extract different p_T points and create unique raw spectra.

Figure 4.42: Gaussian distribution at different p_T points in corrected π^0 spectrum in centrality [0 - 20] %. From these histograms, sigma is extracted and assigned as error on that particular p_T point.

4.13 Systematic Errors

In this section, I will detail the systematic errors from different sources and steps in the analysis. As shown in section 4.10, all steps in this analysis are

connected and thus any change in one of the steps will trickle down and affect every spectrum that comes afterwards. This needs to be carefully considered when calculating the systematic error.

Systematic error from each of the sources and their effects on the four main spectra - corrected π^0 , corrected direct γ single ratio and double ratio are explained in detail below. The systematic error for $R_{dAu}^{\pi^0}$ and R_{dAu} are obtained from the error in the π^0 and direct γ spectra in d+Au and p+p collision system and the error in N_{coll} .

As the procedure is similar regardless of the source of the error, here is an example on how it is done: The χ^2 cut used in this analysis is $\chi^2 < 3.0$. To calculate the systematic error from this step, I consider the $\chi^2 < 2.0$, $\chi^2 < 3.0$ and $\chi^2 < 4.0$. I label these choices as C1, C2 and C3 for the sake of bookkeeping. The choice for this quality cut is done in the procedure at different steps: raw π^0 extraction, raw inclusive γ extraction, π^0 response matrix, η response matrix and single *photon* response matrix. For each C1, C2, C3, the value of χ^2 cut is changed in all of the above steps and the entire chain of analysis is run.

From here we obtain a unique corrected π^0 , correct direct γ , single ratio and double ratio plots for C1, C2 and C3.

C1 and C3 spectra are now compared with C2 spectra and their differences are calculated and plotted as a percentage value (Red and Black open circles). The average of these two differences is also calculated and plotted (closed green circle). The green points are then separately fitted for low and high p_T and this value is assigned as the systematic error from quality cut for each of these spectra. Although this analysis focuses on the high p_T spectra, we have obtained the systematic error on both high and low p_T in case this information is useful for any future analysis with this dataset.

4.13.1 Raw π^0 extraction

The raw π^0 count is extracted by the procedure mentioned in section 4.4 in the mass window of [0.11 - 0.18] GeV (labelled as P2). To calculate the systematic error from this step, this window is changed to [0.10 - 0.17] GeV (labelled as P1) and [0.12 - 0.19] GeV (labelled as P3). The systematic error is calculated as mentioned above for different spectra and presented in Fig. 4.43a to Fig. 4.43d. Note that while the uncertainty in π^0 extraction is slightly higher at high p_T , the resulting uncertainty on the corrected γ is lower. That's because the direct γ / decay γ ratio is very small at low p_T , but it increases at high p_T . Also, there is only a negligible uncertainty from background subtraction due to the low multiplicity of the d+Au collision system.

(a) corrected π^0

(b) corrected direct γ

(c) single ratio

(d) double ratio

Figure 4.43: Systematic error due to raw π^0 counting window

Figure 4.44: Systematic error due to χ^2 cut

4.13.2 Quality (PID) cuts

χ^2 cut

The details of this is mentioned in the example, but repeating important details. C1 is when $\chi^2 < 2.0$ C2 is when $\chi^2 < 3.0$ and C3 is when $\chi^2 < 4.0$. The systematic errors from this PID cut is obtained for different spectra and plotted in Fig.4.44a to Fig.4.44d The results are shown in Figs. 4.44a and 4.44b.

Cut on energy asymmetry

The standard cut on asymmetry for π^0 extraction is 0.8 (labelled as A2); I repeated the analysis with 0.7 (labelled as A1) and 0.9 (labelled as A3). These changes were made in raw π^0 spectrum and π^0 response matrix. The resulting uncertainty from this is plotted from Fig. 4.45a to Fig. 4.45d At large p_T , the systematic error is primarily due to merging effects, along with lack of statistics. As the merging effects are considered separately, these large

(a) corrected π^0

(b) corrected direct γ

(c) single ratio

(d) double ratio

Figure 4.45: Systematic error due to asymmetry cut

values are ignored at this step.

4.13.3 Cut on energy threshold

The standard minimum energy threshold in this analysis is 0.3 GeV (labelled as E2). To calculate systematic error, it was changed to 0.2 GeV (labelled as E1) and 0.4 GeV (labelled as E3). These changes were made in raw π^0 extraction, raw inclusive γ , π^0 response matrix, η response matrix and single γ response matrix.

The results of systematic error from this source is plotted in Fig.4.46a to Fig. 4.46d. As this systematic error affects the first few p_T points, the exact value from the analysis (the green points) has been used mostly and the fitted result is used only for the double ratio.

(a) corrected π^0

(b) corrected direct γ

(c) single ratio

(d) double ratio

Figure 4.46: Systematic error due to minimum energy threshold

Figure 4.47: Systematic error due to minimum energy scaling mismatch

4.13.4 Energy response mismatch between data and simulation

As shown in section 4.5.3, the mean position of the π^0 peak has to be consistent between data and simulation. This ensures that the exact response of the tower for each cluster is captured by the simulation. The fitting function from this process still has a residual error of 0.5%. So systematic error is calculated from this step by changing the scaling factor up and down by 0.5% (labelled as U3 and U1 respectively). This is changed in π^0 response matrix, η response matrix and single γ response matrix. The result of the systematic error from this source is plotted from Fig.4.47a to Fig. 4.47d.

4.13.5 η/π^0 ratio

This ratio is obtained from global fits using gaussian regression method. This method reports systematic errors to the fits. The corrected η spectrum was first obtained using the central value of the ratio. The systematic error from

Figure 4.48: Systematic error from the systematic error of η/π^0 ratio

this was then accounted for by considering the ratio as ± 1.5 Sigma/error (labelled as R1 and R3 respectively) away from the central value. The open black and red circle are very close to one other and thus not visible in the plot at this specific scale of y-axis. This change explicitly affects the corrected η spectrum. The result of the systematic error from this source is plotted from Fig.4.48b to Fig. 4.48d.

4.13.6 Normalization of MB and ERT

Range of fit at high p_T in the method of bootstrapping

The MB- and ERT-triggered dataset are normalised by the method of bootstrapping as mentioned in Sec.4.4.4. To obtain the normalization constant, the spectra after first normalization was fitted in the range [8-20] GeV (labelled as B2). I changed this range to [7-20] GeV (labelled as B1) and [9-20] GeV (labelled as B3). This change was done to raw π^0 spectrum and raw inclusive γ . The resulting systematic error from this is given from Fig. 4.49a to Fig.

(a) corrected π^0

(b) corrected direct γ

Figure 4.49: Systematic error due to normalization by bootstrapping

(a) corrected π^0

(b) corrected direct γ

Figure 4.50: Systematic error due to statistical error in π^0 spectrum from AN1152

4.49b Note: The systematic error from this drops to zero in the single and double ratio at all p_T .

Statistical error from results published in AN1152

For obtaining normalization by bootstrapping, we used the central value of the results published in AN1152 and compared it to corrected π^0 spectrum from this analysis. As this result from AN1152 has its own statistical errors, the spectra is moved to $\pm 1.5\sigma$ (labelled as S1 and S3) at every p_T and the normalization is recalculated. This affects raw π^0 and raw inclusive γ spectrum. The resulting systematic error from this is given from Fig. 4.50a to Fig. 4.50b Note: The systematic error from this drops to zero in the single and double ratio at all p_T

Figure 4.51: Systematic error from choice of transition region between MB and ERT dataset

Transition region

In this analysis, all spectra points below 6.5 GeV is obtained from MB-triggered dataset and above 6.5 GeV is obtained from ERT-triggered dataset. This choice is based on where the statistics of MB runs out and the ERT data points are well beyond the trigger threshold. Systematic error is calculated from varying this transition momentum to 6 GeV and 7 GeV (labelled as T1 and T3 respectively for the sake of book-keeping). As the raw spectra are corrected using the matrix unfolding method, this choice of transition momentum affects the neighbouring points and leaves the rest of the spectra unaffected. So instead of fitting at low p_T and high p_T , we obtain the exact percentage of systematic error for points 3.75 GeV, 4.25 GeV and 7.75, 8.25 GeV. Rest of the points in the transition region are anyway ignored in the analysis due to lack of statistics, so their systematic errors aren't noted.

4.13.7 Conversion photons

Photons are lost to conversion (e^+, e^-) pairs at different layers of detector sub-system. This has already been accounted for in the simulation when correcting different spectra. But there can be a mismatch between the radiation length in detector material between the data and simulation and this contributes to systematic errors. Wenqing Fan did a detailed analysis on this (Ref. Wenqing Fan's thesis Section 4.8.2.3) and obtained the total difference in conversion probability in data and simulation. She estimates the overall conversion probability at 15% with an error of $\pm 3\%$. I have considered the same error value for calculating the systematic error in my analysis.

Effect on π^0 s

The probability of a photon to have not converted is $(1 - p_{conv})$. As we use two photon to reconstruct the π^0 s, the probability of reconstruction is given as $(1 - p_{conv}) * (1 - p_{conv})$. When this equation is calculated for 15% conversion probability and 18% conversion probability, the difference is 7%. This means, if the conversion probability (in effect the radiation length from material) between data and simulation is off by +3%, that affects the π^0 s spectrum by +7%. Note: This is an overestimate at high p_T as the conversion pairs at high p_T still reach the detector and create an EM shower, which crosses our PID cuts and is effectively registered as a photon. But at low p_T , this is a reasonable estimate as most converted pairs are lost before it reaches the EMCal.

Effect on direct γ

The initial conversion probability of approximately 15% suggests that for every 100 photons which are created in the collision (from hadron decays or from direct photon), 85 of them reach the detector unaffected and 15 of them convert to e^+e^- pairs (without considering the acceptance of the detector). A change of +3% (-3%) in conversion probability means out of 100 photons, 82 (88) reach the EMCal unaffected and 18(12) convert to e^+e^- pairs. This in effect means for a 3% change in number of photons, leads to a 20% shift in the number of e^+e^- pairs. To calculate the systematic error, we considered the following response matrices : Decay Photons from π^0 , Decay photons from η and Direct photons. For a change of +3% (-3%) radiation length, the photon clusters were weighted by a factor of 0.97 (1.03) and the electron and positron clusters were weighted by a factor of 1.2 (0.8). These two choices are labelled as V1 and V3. The corrected π^0 spectrum is also modified for these choices. For +3% conversion probability in simulation means for the same observed

Figure 4.52: Systematic error from radiation length mismatch between data and simulation

raw π^0 , corrected π^0 will be 7% larger. The systematic error from each of these choices are thus calculated and its average effect is plotted for correct direct γ , single ratio and the double ratio. This is shown in Fig. 4.52b to 4.52d.

4.13.8 Hadron contamination

This is calculated as detailed in Sec 4.8.1. At first pass, in estimating systematic error from this step, we have assumed “a worst scenario” wherein the half the factor of hadron contamination is considered as the systematic error: therefore the modified inclusive photon is changed by a factor of $0.5 \cdot (1 - R(p_T))$. This new spectra is then used to obtain a new raw direct photon and a new corrected direct photon spectrum. Fig.4.53b is the absolute percentage difference between this new corrected direct γ spectrum and the central value of corrected direct photon obtained in Section 9.2. This is fitted with a Lan-

Figure 4.53: Systematic error from hadron contamination. Shaded region at low p_T is where there is no reasonable prediction for systematic error from this source.

dau function and is considered as p_T dependent systematic error (only) in the negative direction. This relative systematic error propagates exactly to the single ratio and is cancelled in double ratio.

Note: This clearly is an overestimation as I have separately considered systematic error from χ^2 cut and cut on energy threshold and these definitely have an overlap with the systematic error from hadron contamination.

4.13.9 Merging of decay photon clusters

When we slice the π^0 yield in asymmetry bins, it should ideally be equally probable to find a π^0 of a certain momentum in any of them. This isn't what is observed. At very large asymmetric values, we lose a lot of π^0 s due to the acceptance of the detector. This loss is well understood in simulation and compensated for (see Sec. 4.7). At smaller asymmetric values, the two clusters

of the decay photons come together and there is a leakage of energy from one cluster to another. This is a p_T dependent effect and affects higher momentum π^0 s more. This is quite well described in simulation as demonstrated by comparing relative yields in various asymmetric bins between 500 GeV p+p data and GEANT simulation [42].

In AN1152, a systematic error is assigned to the π^0 spectrum using the above comparison and their differences. This p_T dependent systematic error is shown in Fig.4.54a. This systematic error is fitted with a function and the values at different p_T are obtained by evaluating the functional form ($X(p_T)$).

The effect of this systematic error is calculated for direct photons by moving the π^0 spectrum by $1 \mp X(p_T)$ (labelled as M1 and M3 respectively. The central value is M2). For each of these choices the entire chain of analysis is done and a unique correct direct γ spectrum is obtained. M1 and M3 are then compared to the M2 spectrum and their percentage difference and its average is shown in Fig. 4.54b.

Why is the difference in direct photon significantly lower than the difference in π^0 s? Because although a large systematic error in π^0 s affect the raw decay gamma spectrum equally, as you go to higher values of p_T , the inclusive photons are more dominated by the direct photon and less by the decay of hadrons, thus the effect of systematic error is lower. Exact average values are used here without applying any fits for direct γ spectrum and a linear fit for single ratio (Fig.4.54c). The systematic error on double ratio drops to zero.

(a) corrected π^0 from AN1152

(b) corrected direct γ

(c) single ratio

(d) double ratio

Figure 4.54: Systematic error from merging of clusters when they are very close to each other

4.13.10 Tables of systematic error from different sources

p_T	π^0 ext	χ^2 cut	asym	emin	scaling	RL	total (\pm)
0.75	0.74	2.86	0.77	41.6	2.4	7	42.37
1.25	0.74	2.86	0.77	10.97	2.42	7	13.59
1.75	0.74	2.86	0.77	4.45	2.43	7	9.17
2.25	0.74	2.86	0.77	2.75	2.45	7	8.48
2.75	0.74	2.86	0.77	1.79	2.48	7	8.23
3.25	0.74	2.86	0.77	0.9	2.51	7	8.09
3.75	0.74	2.86	0.77	0.98	2.54	7	8.11
4.25	0.74	2.86	0.77	0	2.58	7	8.06

Table 4.3: Percentage systematic error from different sources and total error on low p_T corrected π^0 spectrum.

p_T	π^0 ext	χ^2 cut	asym	scaling	norm.	RL	merging	total (\pm)
7.25	1.47	3.06	0.91	2.91	5.22	7	0.13	11.15
7.75	1.47	3.06	0.91	2.98	2.28	7	0.25	8.98
8.25	1.47	3.06	0.91	3.05	2.28	7	0.39	9.01
8.75	1.47	3.06	0.91	3.13	2.28	7	0.54	9.05
9.25	1.47	3.06	0.91	3.21	2.28	7	0.7	9.09
9.75	1.47	3.06	0.91	3.3	2.28	7	0.88	9.13
11	1.47	3.06	0.91	3.54	2.28	7	1.4	9.29
13	1.47	3.06	0.91	3.98	2.28	7	2.42	9.67
15	1.47	3.06	0.91	4.5	2.28	7	3.68	10.27
17	1.47	3.06	0.91	5.08	2.28	7	5.18	11.15
19	1.47	3.06	0.91	5.74	2.28	7	6.92	12.35
21	1.47	3.06	0.91	6.47	2.28	7	8.9	13.89
23.5	1.47	3.06	0.91	7.48	2.28	7	11.71	16.28

Table 4.4: Percentage systematic error from different sources and total error on high p_T corrected π^0 spectrum.

p_T	π^0 ext	χ^2 cut	asym	scaling	η/π^0	norm.	RL	HC	merging	Total(\pm)
7.25	1.35	4.88	0.92	3.15	3.87	10	10.5	7.07	0.75	17.67
7.75	1.35	4.82	0.92	3.15	3.87	3.54	9.77	6.3	0.98	14.13
8.25	1.35	4.77	0.92	3.15	3.87	4.04	9.1	5.5	1.19	13.46
8.75	1.35	4.74	0.92	3.15	3.87	2.13	8.47	4.74	1.39	12.28
9.25	1.35	4.73	0.92	3.15	3.87	2.13	7.89	4.07	1.58	11.65
9.75	1.35	4.73	0.92	3.15	3.87	2.13	7.34	3.5	1.76	11.12
11	1.35	4.8	0.92	3.15	3.87	2.13	6.14	2.41	2.14	10.16
13	1.35	5.12	0.92	3.15	3.87	2.13	4.61	1.42	2.6	9.4
15	1.35	5.7	0.92	3.15	3.87	2.13	3.47	0.9	2.85	9.25
17	1.35	6.54	0.92	3.15	3.87	2.13	2.6	0.61	2.91	9.51
19	1.35	7.63	0.92	3.15	3.87	2.13	1.96	0.44	2.76	10.1
21	1.35	8.98	0.92	3.15	3.87	2.13	1.47	0.33	2.41	10.99
23.5	1.35	11.02	0.92	3.15	3.87	2.13	1.03	0.24	1.7	12.56

Table 4.5: Percentage systematic error from different sources and total error on high p_T corrected direct γ spectrum.

p_T	π^0 ext	χ^2 cut	asym	scaling	η/π^0	norm.	RL	HC	merging	Total(\pm)
7.25	2.77	4.09	1.54	4.68	3.91	0	17.1	7.07	0.94	20.18
7.75	2.77	3.48	1.54	4.5	3.91	4.01	16.61	6.3	1.27	19.77
8.25	2.77	2.97	1.54	4.35	3.91	1.09	16.12	5.5	1.61	18.63
8.75	2.77	2.55	1.54	4.22	3.91	0	15.65	4.74	1.95	17.92
9.25	2.77	2.23	1.54	4.12	3.91	0	15.2	4.07	2.29	17.32
9.75	2.77	2.01	1.54	4.05	3.91	0	14.76	3.5	2.63	16.81
11	2.77	1.89	1.54	4.01	3.91	0	13.71	2.41	3.51	15.84
13	2.77	2.97	1.54	4.3	3.91	0	12.18	1.42	4.97	15.09
15	2.77	5.61	1.54	5.05	3.91	0	10.83	0.9	6.47	15.56
17	2.77	9.83	1.54	6.26	3.91	0	9.62	0.61	8.04	17.85
19	2.77	15.61	1.54	7.92	3.91	0	8.55	0.44	9.66	22.32
21	2.77	22.96	1.54	10.04	3.91	0	7.6	0.33	11.33	28.97
23.5	2.77	34.35	1.54	13.32	3.91	0	6.56	0.24	13.51	40.1

Table 4.6: Percentage systematic error from different sources and total error on high p_T single ratio.

p_T	π^0 ext	χ^2 cut	asym	scaling	η/π^0	norm.	RL	HC	merging	Total(\pm)
7.25	3.18	1.46	2.77	1.12	1.61	0	0.63	0.32	0.39	4.94
7.75	3.18	1.47	2.77	1.12	1.61	1.41	0.63	0.32	0.39	5.14
8.25	3.18	1.49	2.77	1.12	1.61	1.16	0.63	0.32	0.39	5.08
8.75	3.18	1.55	2.77	1.12	1.61	0	0.63	0.32	0.39	4.97
9.25	3.18	1.62	2.77	1.12	1.61	0	0.63	0.32	0.39	4.99
9.75	3.18	1.72	2.77	1.12	1.61	0	0.63	0.32	0.39	5.02
11	3.18	2.06	2.77	1.12	1.61	0	0.63	0.32	0.39	5.15
13	3.18	2.91	2.77	1.12	1.61	0	0.63	0.32	0.39	5.54
15	3.18	4.13	2.77	1.12	1.61	0	0.63	0.32	0.39	6.27
17	3.18	5.72	2.77	1.12	1.61	0	0.63	0.32	0.39	7.41
19	3.18	7.67	2.77	1.12	1.61	0	0.63	0.32	0.39	9.01
21	3.18	9.99	2.77	1.12	1.61	0	0.63	0.32	0.39	11.05
23.5	3.18	13.41	2.77	1.12	1.61	0	0.63	0.32	0.39	14.22

Table 4.7: Percentage systematic error from different sources and total error on high p_T double ratio.

Chapter 5

Results and Discussions

The unfolding procedure discussed in detail corrects the raw π^0 and direct γ s spectrum for acceptance, efficiency and smearing. As the simulation is done over unit rapidity, the spectra are also normalised to unit rapidity. Thus the invariant yield as defined in 5.1 is obtained from the corrected spectra by dividing by $(1/2\pi p_T)$.

$$\frac{1}{2\pi p_T} \frac{1}{N_{events}} \frac{dN^{\pi^0/\gamma}}{dp_T d\eta} \quad (5.1)$$

PHENIX took data with d+Au collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 200 \text{ GeV}$ for only three runs : 2003, 2008 and 2016. These are known as Run3, Run8 and Run16 respectively.

Run Number	π^0 (MB)	π^0 (Centrality)	direct γ (MB)	direct γ (Centrality)
Run3	✓	✓	✓	✗
Run8	✓	✓	✗	✗
Run16	✓	✓	✓	✓

Table 5.1: Run numbers and analysis done with each dataset.

In the following section, I will be presenting the invariant yield of π^0 s and direct γ s in minimum bias and in four different centrality classes : [0-20]%, [20-40]%, [40-60]%, [60-88]%. Statistical and systematic errors are plotted in this

using lines and bars respectively. I will also be comparing results from this analysis to previously published results where possible.

Note: all of the spectra plotted below are corrected for centrality bias factor. Details of these can be found PHENIX analysis note#900. Here, I just tabulate the final numbers that these spectra at different centralities are multiplied by.

Centrality	bias factor
0-20%	0.941
20-40%	1.000
40-60%	1.034
60-88%	1.031
0-88%	0.889

Table 5.2: Centrality bias factor

5.1 Invariant yield of π^0 s

In this section, I present the invariant yield of π^0 s measured at $|\eta| < 0.35$ from the $\pi^0 \rightarrow \gamma\gamma$ decay channel at $\sqrt{s} = 200\text{GeV}$ from Run16 d+Au collisions. These are presented separately at low p_T [0.75 - 4.25 GeV] and high p_T [7.75 - 17 GeV] for minimum bias and in four different centrality bins.

(a) minimum bias

(b) centrality binned

Figure 5.1: Invariant yield of π^0 s at low p_T in Run16 d+Au collisions with statistical and systematic errors.

(a) minimum bias

(b) centrality binned

Figure 5.2: Invariant yield of π^0 s at high p_T in Run16 d+Au collisions with statistical and systematic errors.

Figure 5.3: Invariant yield of π^0 in minimum bias from Run16 and Run3 d+Au collisions at 200GeV. Data are from [44].

5.2 Comparing invariant π^0 yield with previously published results

In this section, we compare the minimum bias invariant yield from this analysis to the published data from [43]. In addition to this, we have also compared the yield in different centrality bins as published in [44]. These are shown from Fig.5.3a to Fig.5.6.

Figure 5.4: Invariant yield of corrected π^0 at low p_T in different centralities from Run16 and Run3 d+Au collisions at 200GeV. Data from [44].

Figure 5.5: Ratio of corrected π^0 at low p_T in different centralities from Run16 and Run3 d+Au collisions at 200GeV. Data from [44].

Figure 5.6: Invariant yield of corrected π^0 at high p_T in different centralities from Run16 and Run3 d+Au collisions at 200 GeV. Data from [44].

Figure 5.7: Ratio of corrected π^0 at high p_T in different centralities from Run16 and Run3 d+Au collisions at 200 GeV. Data from [44].

Figure 5.8: Invariant yield of direct γ at high p_T in Run16 d+Au collisions with statistical and systematic errors.

5.3 Invariant yield of direct γ s.

The invariant yield of direct γ s measured at $|\eta| < 0.35$ obtained by subtracting decay γ from inclusive photons and correcting with simulation at $\sqrt{s} = 200 \text{ GeV}$ from Run16 is presented here. These are presented for high p_T [7.75 - 17] GeV.

5.4 Comparing invariant direct γ yield with previously published results

In [45], the the invariant yield of direct photon for minimum bias d+Au collisions using Run 3 data from PHENIX is presented. The value of the spectra at different p_T can be found in the appendix section of AN1065.

In this PPG, they also present the parameterized fit to direct photon cross-section in p+p collision obtained from Run3 data set.

$$E \frac{d^3\sigma}{dp^3} = a \cdot p_T^{-(b+c \cdot \ln x_T)} \cdot (1 - x_T^2)^2 \quad (5.2)$$

where $x_T = 2p_T/\sqrt{s}$. The parameters of fit to p+p data are $a = 6.6 *$

Figure 5.9: Comparing high p_T direct photon cross section from Run 3 data as done in [45] and this analysis. Also shown in figure is the parameterized scaled fit from p+p data and theoretical curves (obtained from Prof. Werner Vogelsang via private communication) scaled from nucleon-nucleon collision under three different renormalization scales.

10^{-3} , $b = 6.4$, $c = 0.4$, $n = 17.6$. This fit function when scaled by $\langle N_{coll} \rangle = 7.59$ (0-88%) and normalised to the inelastic cross-section of d+Au collision ($\sigma_{dAu} = 2240mb$) to the inelastic cross-section of p+p collisions ($\sigma_{pp} = 42mb$) should agree with our results.

Note in [45], their reported cross-section is multiplied by the bias factor of 0.98. For consistency in comparison, the cross-section for this analysis has also been multiplied by the corresponding bias factor of 0.889 that has been used in recent publications of PHENIX collaborations.

As shown in Fig. 5.9a, the data points from [45] for cross-section, the scaled parameterized fit, the theory curve and the data points from this analysis all agree with one another within their uncertainties.

5.5 Ratio of direct γ over π^0

We first begin by making some general remarks about the ratio of direct γ over π^0 . This ratio is expected to increase with p_T , this can be understood by looking at the the cross-section of particle production given by Eq. 1.8. At

least to leading order (2x2 processes), if the final state object is a π^0 , it comes from jet fragmentation, a fraction of the parton's momentum, whereas if it is a photon, it carries the full momentum of the scattered parton at all transverse momenta. Therefore the cross-section of π^0 s will fall faster than direct γ s and thus the ratio increases with p_T .

Before presenting the results, I reiterate the motivation, already mentioned in Sec. 2.3, to look at this ratio in different centrality bins using Au+Au as an example.

5.5.1 Results from Au+Au collision system

In Au+Au collision, we expect and have observed the formation of QGP. This observation was validated by four powerful R_{AA} results.

- Suppression in π^0 production in minimum bias [38].
- Lack of suppression in high p_T direct γ production in minimum bias [46].
- Centrality binned results of π^0 production showed more suppression in central collision and vanishing suppression as we move to peripheral bins [47].
- Centrality binned results of direct γ production at high p_T showed lack of suppression at all class of centrality events [48].

Now let us look at the ratio of direct γ over π^0 in different centrality bins. What do we expect? The numerator is (to first order approximation) not modified for different centralities whereas the denominator is modified due to the modification in QGP medium formation for collisions with different impact parameter. Therefore this ratio will show distinct trend lines for different centralities.

This ratio plot here is obtained by using the invariant yield of yield of π^0 s from [38] and invariant yield of direct γ from [23].

Note: Only centrality bins (20-30)%, (30-40)%, (40-50)%, (50-60)% and (0-92)% were commonly tabulated between these two analysis. All other centralities like (0-10)%, (10-20)% etc. are tabulated for π^0 s and it is derived for direct γ from its minimum bias spectrum under the reasonable assumption that the direct photon spectra at different centrality scale with N_{coll} .

These plots show us what we expected : A clear centrality dependent ordering in the ratio of direct γ over π^0 s in Au+Au collision systems. Both in Figs. 5.10a and 5.10b the ratios for the most central collisions are about

Figure 5.10: Single and double ratio plots for Au+Au collision system at 200 GeV.

a factor of 5 higher than for the most peripheral ones, corresponding to the factor of 5 suppression of the π^0 spectra in central collisions. In other words, all changes in the ratios come from the denominator (π^0).

5.5.2 Results from d+Au collision system

In the d+Au collision system, the suppression of π^0 production in central collisions could, on the face of it, be interpreted as a sign of formation of QGP droplets¹. If this were true, d+Au collision behaved similar to Au+Au collision. That implies, direct γ will be unaffected and the ratio of direct γ to π^0 for d+Au at different centralities will look similar to the Au+Au results, the ratios would be separated for centralities the same way as the $\pi^0 R_{AA}$ alone is.

¹Note, however, that usually suppression is explained as radiative (and/or collisional) energy loss of the parton while traversing the medium, i.e. it requires a certain path-length within the QGP, and it is unclear how a small droplet could effectively slow down a parton. On the other hand we should point out, that *lack of* suppression in d+Au itself would *not* prove the *absence* of a QGP droplet! Our findings do not invalidate other results (notably those on azimuthal asymmetries), whatever their explanation might be. Also note, that even if the QGP droplets could cause energy loss, like in Au+Au, this alone would not explain the apparent *enhancement* of the $\pi^0 R_{dAu}$ in peripheral collisions.

Figure 5.11: Single and double ratio plots for d+Au collision system at 200 GeV in the 7.5 GeV to 17 GeV range.

I now present the ratio of invariant yield of direct photon over invariant yield of π^0 s in different centrality bins, at high p_T (7.5 GeV/ c to 18 GeV/ c) in Fig. 5.11a. A double ratio is also plotted as shown in Fig. 5.11b, wherein we divide the direct γ over π^0 s at different centralities by the ratio obtained for minimum bias. This reduces the systematic uncertainties by a factor of 3. The systematic error on an average for the single ratio is around 15%, whereas for the double ratio, it is around 5%.

From these plots, it is obvious that the γ_{dir}/π^0 ratios in for d+Au collision are very different from that observed in Au+Au collisions. In these, the ratios for various centralities DO NOT show distinct trend lines for different centralities. This is inconsistent with the assumption that the observed suppression/enhancement for π^0 is an effect of medium formation in d+Au systems. We speculate as detailed in Sec. 2.2, that there is a p_T dependent bias in centrality determination in small systems thus affecting the binning of both π^0 s and direct γ s. This effect gets cancelled when the ratio is plotted and thus showing no centrality dependence. Note, that other, small, second-order effects are *not* excluded due to the limited precision of the data.

5.6 Nuclear Modification Factor (R_{AB})

We restate the equation for R_{AB} here,

$$R_{AB}(p_T) = \frac{\left(\frac{d^2N}{dp_T d\eta}\right)_{AB}}{\langle N_{coll} \rangle_{AB} * \left(\frac{d^2N}{dp_T d\eta}\right)_{pp}} = \frac{Y(AB)}{\langle N_{coll} \rangle_{AB} * Y(pp)} \quad (5.3)$$

We now have the individual spectra of π^0 and direct γ for minimum bias and for different centralities from d+Au collision. The value of $\langle N_{coll} \rangle_{AB}$ for different event classes is given in table 2.1. The π^0 and direct γ in p+p collisions are obtained from [26] and PHENIX Analysis Note #1371 respectively. This by definition is not binned in separate centrality classes.

Note, all systematic errors shown in Fig. 5.12 and 5.13 are *correlated* with centralities, i.e, all the points at different centrality move up and down together. This implies that although there is a large uncertainty on the central value of these points, their relative ordering is maintained.

Looking at these plots, here are the following things we can already learn.

- there is a clear centrality based ordering in both π^0 and direct γ .
- the most central events are suppressed (< 1) and peripheral events are enhanced (> 1).
- In central events, the suppression of π^0 s seem to be higher than those of direct γ .
- In most peripheral events, the degree enhancement of π^0 s matches that of direct γ .
- In the given p_T range [7.5 - 18] GeV, to first order, both the π^0 and γ R_{dAu} appear to be flat.

Figure 5.12: R_{dAu} of π^0 for minimum bias and for different centralities. The points at high p_T (>7.5 GeV) are also fitted with a zeroth order polynomial and their fit values with error bars are mentioned in the legend.

Figure 5.13: R_{dAu} of direct γ for minimum bias and for different centralities. The points at high p_T (>7.5 GeV) are also fitted with a zeroth order polynomial and their fit values with error bars are mentioned in the legend.

5.6.1 Deriving N_{coll} from data

Given the above observations, it is clear that the N_{coll} derived for the Glauber model has some intrinsic bias that is affecting both R_{dAu} . We know that the high p_T direct photon is unaffected by final state effect like QGP formation and thus should scale exactly with N_{coll} . Using this knowledge we can now derive N_{coll} *experimentally* from direct photons by dividing the invariant yield obtained in d+Au collisions with the invariant yield obtained in p+p collisions. The results of this is shown in 5.14 and the percentage difference between $N_{coll}^{glauber}$ and N_{coll}^{data} in Fig. 5.15.

$$\langle N_{coll}^{data} \rangle = \frac{\left(\frac{d^2 N^\gamma}{dp_T d\eta}\right)_{dAu}}{\left(\frac{d^2 N^\gamma}{dp_T d\eta}\right)_{pp}} \quad (5.4)$$

The plot Fig. 5.15 on percentage difference says that on an average, the N_{coll} of the sample that we label as “0-20%” is lower than what is expected from Glauber model by about 2-5% (depending on the range of fit) and the N_{coll} of the sample that we label as “60-88%” is higher than what is expected from glauber model by about 15%. Although it is hard to comment on the exact percentage values from these results, they align qualitatively with the suspicion discussed in Sec.2.2.

Events with a high p_T particle come from an interaction of high- x parton within the nucleon of the interacting nucleus. When this high- x parton is present in the nucleon of deuterium nucleus, this (a) severely depletes the energy available for soft particle production [30] or (b) the nucleon with a high- x partons have fewer partons than the average, thus the soft particle production is decreased [34]. But it is this soft particle interaction which dictates the number of charged particles in the forward region (N_{ch}), which in turn is used to determine the centrality class of the event, so any modification to such a production mechanism affects the centrality binning.

In such an event with a high p_T particle, even if the impact parameter is small, i.e it is a true “*central*” event, as the N_{ch} is also small, this will likely get mis-binned as a more peripheral event. Therefore there is a unidirectional migration of events from central to peripheral bins. This translates as a decrease in *true* N_{coll} in central events and increase in *true* N_{coll} in peripheral events.

Under this explanation, it is reasonable to expect that this *true* N_{coll} will have a p_T dependence. In events with larger p_T particle, there is further reduction in soft particle mechanism, thus it gets classified as a more peripheral event. In other words, true central events will be misbinned. But whether it is migrated to an event class with 20-40%, 40-60% or 60-88% depends on

Figure 5.14: Ratio of invariant yield of direct photon in d+Au collision to p+p collision to obtain N_{coll} through a data driven method.

p_T of the produced particle (or x of the interacting parton). But in the plots presented here, there is no strong p_T dependence. This could be just an artifact of limited range in p_T or there is another competing initial state effect that we don't full understand.

Figure 5.15: Percentage difference between $N_{coll}^{glauber}$ and N_{coll}^{data} obtained from Fig. 5.14.

5.7 Renormalising $R_{dAu}^{\pi^0}$ using R_{dAu}^{γ}

Given that we now have derived N_{coll} in a data driven fashion, we can now use this to re-calculate $R_{dAu}^{\pi^0}$. This can be done by simply using N_{coll}^{data} and considering the appropriate systematic error from the fitting procedure or we can use the R_{dAu}^{γ} directly. In this analysis, we chose the latter option.

$$\frac{R_{dAu}^{\pi^0}}{R_{dAu}^{\gamma}} = \frac{(Y_{dAu}^{\pi^0}/Y_{pp}^{\pi^0})}{(Y_{dAu}^{\gamma}/Y_{pp}^{\gamma})} = \frac{(Y_{dAu}^{\pi^0}/Y_{dAu}^{\gamma})}{(Y_{pp}^{\pi^0}/Y_{pp}^{\gamma})} \quad (5.5)$$

Explicitly writing the ratio of $R_{dAu}^{\pi^0}$ and R_{dAu}^{γ} as above reduces the systematic error to the error in the invariant yield of π^0 or γ in d+Au system and p+p system independently. The relative systematic error in d+Au system is the same as that for “single ratio” (Fig. 5.11a), and the systematic error from p+p system for π^0 and γ are presently just added in quadrature. There might be some possible correlation between these errors which could lead to some cancellation, but this has not been considered so far. The results of this modified $R_{dAu}^{\pi^0}$ are shown in Fig. 5.17.

In this plot, there is no strange enhancement in peripheral bins. In fact all values in minimum bias, 20-40%, 40-60% and 60-88% are comparable. The average value in 0-20% for >7.75 GeV appears to have residual suppression. Is this coming from energy loss in QGP in spite of all our previous arguments? It is hard to say with this statistical error. More information can be gained by analysing the 0-20% centrality event class in finer bins of centrality. But that is beyond the scope of this thesis.

Figure 5.16: Modified $R_{dAu}^{\pi^0}$ which is obtained by taking the ratio of $R_{dAu}^{\pi^0}$ to R_{dAu}^{γ} .

5.8 $R_{dAu}^{\pi^0}$ and R_{dAu}^{γ} as a function of parton momentum x

NLO calculations in p+p collision suggest that at the p_T range of interest in this analysis [7 - 18] GeV, the dominant hard scattering process is quark-gluon scattering (Fig. 5.17). High p_T π^0 s are leading hadrons of a jet, carrying only a fraction (albeit large one) of the parent parton energy. On average, leading particles in a jet carry about 75% of the momentum of the jet. As these measurements are made at mid-rapidity, the momentum of the interacting parton is related to the jet and π^0 momentum as follows,

$$x_p = 2p_T^{jet} / \sqrt{s_{NN}} \approx 2p_T^{\pi^0} / (0.75 * \sqrt{s_{NN}}) \quad (5.6)$$

Measurement of γ/π^0 at different $\sqrt{s} = 31, 53, 63 \text{ GeV}$ in p+p collision at CERN, ISR by [49] showed a rising behaviour, similar to Fig. 5.11a above $p_T = 3 \text{ GeV}$ for all collision energies. In addition to this, the exact numerical value of this ratio was consistent with each other within error bars, suggesting that the underlying production mechanism for π^0 s and direct γ s in this momentum range is similar. The photon however carries the full momentum of the interacting parton and thus it is related to x as follows.

$$x_p = 2p_T^{direct\gamma} / \sqrt{s_{NN}} \quad (5.7)$$

Using the above equations, the R_{dAu} plots presented as a function of p_T in Fig. 5.12 and 5.13 is converted to a plot as a function of x . There are several advantages of studying the R_{dAu} as a function of parton momentum x .

- Firstly, the spectra from π^0 and direct γ can now be plotted on the same canvas and studied together as they come from same initial parton interaction as mentioned above. The π^0 spectra have smaller statistical error and the direct γ spectra reach lower values of x , thus merged spectra take advantage of both of these effects.
- This makes it easier to compare R_{dAu} from different collision energies ($\sqrt{s_{NN}}$).
- The model of “shrinking nucleon” in the presence of high- x parton which is detailed in Sec.2.3 makes a prediction for $R_{dAu}(x)$ ².

²Note: this model uses a single parameter ‘ β ’. The value of this parameter is obtained by fitting to published R_{dAu}^{jets} . Caution needs to be applied when using these prediction to study p+Au and He+Au results.

Figure 5.17: Fraction of jet production due to qq , gg and qq processes as a function of x_T from pQCD NLO calculation from [50]. The red box indicates the region in x that is plotted in this analysis.

Figure 5.18: Ratio of γ/π^0 in p+p collision for $\sqrt{s} = 31, 53, 63 \text{ GeV}$ [49].

Figure 5.19: R_{dAu} of π^0 and direct γ as a function of x .

In Fig. 5.19, the results for $R_{dAu}^{p_i^0}$, R_{dAu}^γ , linear fit to both the data-sets and the curve from the “shrinking nucleon” model is plotted. As it can be seen, the model agrees well with the data suggesting that at-least the majority of the x dependence that we see in $R_{dAu}^{\pi^0}$ is from the bias in centrality determination. This is especially true for 0-20% and 60-88%. Using this, we can *maybe* obtain $N_{coll}^{data}(x)$ as a function of x similar to how it is done in Sec. 5.6.1 with $R_{dAu}^\gamma(p_T)$.

Chapter 6

Summary and Future work

In this thesis, we analysed $\sqrt{s} = 200 \text{ GeV}$ d+Au collision data from 2016 dataset using EMCal at PHENIX detector. The primary signals for this analysis are π^0 obtained from invariant mass reconstruction and direct γ s obtained from statistical subtraction of decay γ s from all photons.

A robust technique of correcting the raw spectra with unfolding procedure using response matrix was developed. A separate simulation for Pion, Eta and Single Photon is used to correct π^0 s, obtain decay photons from π^0 s and η s and correct direct γ s. Using the data and simulation, an invariant yield of π^0 s and direct γ s for different centralities was obtained.

Centrality determination using Glauber model for small system was studied by obtaining the ratio of invariant yield of direct γ over π^0 for different centralities (single ratio). This was used as a tool to determine that there is in fact a bias in centrality binning for small systems.

Nuclear modification factor for π^0 s and direct γ s are obtained. A new $R_{dAu}^{\pi^0}$ is obtained with the use of R_{dAu}^{γ} .

Speculations from various theorists and experimentalists are noted in the thesis to understand why Glauber model, a theory so successful in centrality determination in heavy-ion collisions fails for small systems. The $R_{dAu}^{\pi^0}$ and R_{dAu}^{γ} is re-plotted as a function of longitudinal momentum fraction x of the interacting parton and compared with curves from “shrinking nucleon” model.

The question of whether there is truly energy loss at the most central (0-20%) $R_{dAu}^{\pi^0}$ can be further studied by dividing the spectra into finer bins in centrality like 0-5%, 5-10%, 10-15% and 15-20%.

Similar analysis in p+Au and He+Au systems are underway, which (i) will further validate (or invalidate) these results and (ii) the ordering of this single ratio in different collision system will provide us some insights on the initial state effect that leads to such a bias in small systems which vanishes for larger systems.

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